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Knowmad Institut's Comments and Recommendations on the Updated Draft Text of the UN Cybercrime Convention (Mayo 2024)

COMMENTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS TO THE AD HOC COMMITTEE TO ELABORATE A COMPREHENSIVE INTERNATIONAL CONVENTION ON COUNTERING THE USE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGIES FOR CRIMINAL PURPOSES, ON THE UPDATED TEXT OF THE CONVENTION DATED MAY 2024.

European Institute for Multidisciplinary Studies on Human Rights and Sciences - Knowmad Institut.

Special Task Force:

Bp. Martin Ignacio Díaz Velásquez, Prof. Jorge Vicente Paladines, PhD. Leticia Fuentes Vera, Eng. Jesús Alfredo Ribero Faria, MSc. Oscar Hugo Espin García, Rev. Daniela Kreher, MSc. Ludwing Moncada Bellorin.

INTRODUCTION

The **Knowmad Institut - European Institute for Multidisciplinary Studies on Human Rights and Sciences**, committed to promoting human dignity and sustainable development, presents the following comments and recommendations for the updated text of the **International Convention On Countering The Use Of Information And Communications Technologies For Criminal Purposes ([A/AC.291/22/Rev.3](#))**. These recommendations are based on a detailed analysis of the draft convention, the supplementary documents with references [A/AC.291/25/Rev.1](#) and [A/AC.291/27](#), and the previous contributions of the Knowmad Institute to this distinguished committee ([Recs. 3ra Sesión](#); [Recs. 4ta Sesión](#)). Our approach focuses on ensuring that the convention protects human rights and dignity, promotes international cooperation, and adopts a balanced and effective approach to combating cybercrime.

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PREAMBLE

The Knowmad Institute, known for its multidisciplinary approach to human rights and science studies, has actively participated in previous sessions of the Ad Hoc Committee to elaborate a comprehensive international convention against the criminal use of information and communication technologies (ICT). In our previous contributions, we emphasized the importance of a balanced and comprehensive approach that respects the right to anonymity and personal data protection to create safe spaces in cyberspace. However, the most crucial aspect we highlighted was the need for promoting and protecting human rights to be the primary objectives when regulating ICT. This ensures that access to technology improves the quality of life without infringing on rights and freedoms, a principle of utmost importance.

We proposed the inclusion of a specific clause to protect vulnerable groups and prioritize the inclusive representation of individuals exposed to conflicts or persecutions of a political, ethnic, religious, or migratory nature. Furthermore, we emphasized the need to adopt an intersectional human rights approach with a gender perspective and the relevance of open science as a tool to prevent the criminal use of information and communication technologies (ICT). We consider it particularly urgent to address the potential threats of persecution due to migratory origin, recognizing that the diversity of dialects, especially in regions of the global south, can be mistakenly interpreted as an “encryption” method for possible criminal messages. This perspective is essential to strengthen international cooperation in preventing cybercrime and hybrid crimes, as well as in the interception of telecommunications, ensuring an inclusive and non-discriminatory approach to crime prevention.

We underscore the collective concern about the challenges posed by outsourced espionage services and intelligence gathering, highlighting the need for rigorous regulation and oversight to protect the physical integrity of individuals within organized civil society in particular and society in general. Additionally, we addressed the issue of trafficking controlled substances via the Internet and its impact on public health, suggesting harm reduction and deflection strategies to mitigate the adverse effects on the community.

DESCRIPTION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Regarding the Preamble

Description

The convention's preamble clearly establishes the need and purpose of the international agreement to combat the criminal use of information and communication technologies (ICT). The inclusion of aspects such as the potential negative impact of ICT on society and the need for a global criminal justice policy are well-founded points. However, specificity in some points could be improved to strengthen the document's precision.

It is vital to include freedom of expression as a fundamental right. This is a delicate issue because the criteria for limiting such freedom must also be agreed upon, ensuring that the expression does not harm others.

Recommendations

- The preamble underscores the importance of a global criminal justice policy to protect society against cybercrime, highlighting the need for effective international cooperation and the strengthening of national capacities (United Nations, 2016). Ultimately, the protection of individuals, businesses, democracy, the rule of law, and the environment (European Union, 2024).
- It is suggested to incorporate more precise definitions of key terms used in the convention, such as "cybercrime" and "ICT," to avoid ambiguous interpretations and ensure uniform application of the document.
- Furthermore, a greater emphasis on protecting privacy and individuals' digital rights is recommended, including explicit references to existing human rights frameworks, such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) (United Nations, 1966; United Nations, 2016).
- The rapid technological evolution makes it crucial for the document to contemplate the need for periodic reviews and updates to incorporate new technologies and emerging methodologies.

Article 1. Statement of purpose

Original Text

The purposes of this Convention are to:

- (a) Promote and strengthen measures to prevent and combat cybercrime more efficiently and effectively; [agreed ad referendum]
- (b) Promote, facilitate and strengthen international cooperation in preventing and combating cybercrime; and [agreed ad referendum]

- (c) Promote, facilitate and support technical assistance and capacity-building to prevent and combat cybercrime, in particular for the benefit of developing countries.

Description

Article 1 sets out key objectives for the convention, such as the prevention of cybercrime, international cooperation, and technical assistance. However, for greater effectiveness and fairness in its application, it is crucial to explicitly include the protection of human rights and privacy, as well as the need for periodic reviews of the strategies adopted.

Recommendations

1. **Incorporate the Protection of Human Rights and Privacy:** It is essential to ensure that all measures adopted under this convention respect human rights and the privacy of individuals. This can be achieved by explicitly referencing existing human rights frameworks, such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) (United Nations, 1966). This approach not only protects fundamental freedoms but also reinforces the legitimacy of actions against cybercrime.
2. **Specify the Need for Continuous Updates:** The rapid technological evolution requires regularly reviewing and updating strategies and measures to combat cybercrime. Including a periodic evaluation and updates mechanism ensures that the convention remains relevant and effective in the face of new threats and technological developments.

Article 2. Use of terms

Original Text

For the purposes of this Convention:

- (a) “Information and communications technology system” shall mean any device or group of interconnected or related devices, one or more of which, pursuant to a program, gathers, stores and performs automatic processing of electronic data;
- (b) “Electronic data” shall mean any representation of facts, information or concepts in a form suitable for processing in an information and communications technology system, including a program suitable to cause an information and communications technology system to perform a function;

(c) “Traffic data” shall mean any electronic data relating to a communication by means of an information and communications technology system, generated by an information and communications technology system that formed a part in the chain of communication, indicating the communication’s origin, destination, route, time, date, size, duration or type of underlying service;

(d) “Content data” shall mean any electronic data, other than subscriber information or traffic data, relating to the substance of the data transferred by an information and communications technology system, including, but not limited to, images, text messages, voice messages, audio recordings and video recordings; [agreed ad referendum]

(e) “Service provider” shall mean:

(i) Any public or private entity that provides to users of its service the ability to communicate by means of an information and communications technology system; and

(ii) Any other entity that processes or stores electronic data on behalf of such a communications service or users of such a service;

(f) “Subscriber information” shall mean any information that is held by a service provider, relating to subscribers of its services other than traffic or content data and by which can be established:

(i) The type of communications service used, the technical provisions taken thereto and the period of service;

(ii) The subscriber’s identity, postal or geographical address, telephone and other access number, billing and payment information, available on the basis of the service agreement or arrangement;

(iii) Any other information on the site of the installation of communications equipment, available on the basis of the service agreement or arrangement;

(g) “Personal data” shall mean any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person;

(h) “Serious crime” shall mean conduct constituting an offence punishable by a maximum deprivation of liberty of at least four years or a more serious penalty;

(i) “Property” shall mean assets of every kind, whether corporeal or incorporeal, movable or immovable, tangible or intangible, including virtual

assets, and legal documents or instruments evidencing title to, or interest in, such assets;

(j) “Proceeds of crime” shall mean any property derived from or obtained, directly or indirectly, through the commission of an offence; [agreed in informals]

(k) “Freezing” or “seizure” shall mean temporarily prohibiting the transfer, conversion, disposition or movement of property or temporarily assuming custody or control of property on the basis of an order issued by a court or other competent authority; [agreed in informals]

(l) “Confiscation”, which includes forfeiture where applicable, shall mean the permanent deprivation of property by order of a court or other competent authority; [agreed in informals]

(m) “Predicate offence” shall mean any offence as a result of which proceeds have been generated that may become the subject of an offence as defined in article 17 of this Convention; [agreed in informals]

(n) “Regional economic integration organization” shall mean an organization constituted by sovereign States of a given region to which its member States have transferred competence in respect of matters governed by this Convention and which has been duly authorized, in accordance with its internal procedures, to sign, ratify, accept, approve or accede to it; references to “States Parties” under this Convention shall apply to such organizations within the limits of their competence;

(o) “Emergency” shall mean a situation in which there is a significant and imminent risk to the life or safety of any natural person.

Description

Article 2 provides clear and detailed definitions of key terms used in the convention. However, to enhance the comprehensiveness and relevance of these definitions, the following recommendations should be considered:

In section “(b)”, it is necessary to specify that data created by Artificial Intelligence (AI) should be treated the same as data created by humans.

In section “(i)”, the issue of Crime Product (PI) is significantly affecting artists, as new works—video, image, audio, etc.—are being created using AI. However, it is unclear whether many of these works can be classified as plagiarism offenses (the treatment of these issues is still under study) with maximum deprivation of liberty.

Recommendations

1. **Update and Expand Definitions:** Consider including additional definitions that reflect emerging technologies and practices, such as Artificial Intelligence, the Internet of Things (IoT), and blockchain. This will ensure that the convention remains relevant and applicable in a constantly changing technological environment (Weber, 2009; Lobach et al., 2021).
2. **Clarification of Technical Terms:** To avoid misunderstandings, it is suggested to provide specific examples or usage scenarios for some technical terms, such as "content data" and "traffic data." This could include annexes with practical use cases.
3. **Periodic Review of Definitions:** Establish a mechanism for the periodic review and update of definitions, ensuring they adapt to new technologies and cybercrime methodologies. This proactive approach can help maintain the effectiveness of the convention over time (Aulia, 2023; Gunarto et al., 2023).

Article 3. Scope of application

Original Text

This Convention shall apply, except as otherwise stated herein, to:

- (a) The prevention, investigation and prosecution of the criminal offences established in accordance with this Convention, including the freezing, seizure, confiscation and return of the proceeds from such offences;
- (b) The collecting, obtaining, preserving and sharing of evidence in electronic form for the purpose of criminal investigations or proceedings, as provided for in articles 23 and 35 of this Convention.

Description

Article 3 clearly defines the scope of the convention, establishing that it will apply to the prevention, investigation, and prosecution of cybercrimes, as well as to international cooperation in these aspects. However, to ensure effective and fair application, it is important to consider some additional recommendations.

Recommendations

1. **Inclusion of Human Rights and Privacy Protection:** It is essential to ensure that the application of this convention respects human rights and privacy. This can be achieved by adding a clause that guarantees all measures adopted are compatible with international human rights standards, such as those established in the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) (United Nations, 1966).

2. **Specification of Oversight Mechanisms:** It is suggested to establish oversight mechanisms to ensure that measures adopted under this convention are applied fairly and effectively. This could include the creation of an independent oversight committee that regularly evaluates policies and practices related to cybercrime (Ruslan, 2023).
3. **Reference to International Standards:** Including explicit references to other relevant international standards can help contextualize and reinforce the principles established in the convention. This includes standards on human rights, privacy, and data protection, as well as applicable technical and legal standards (Bunga, 2019).

Article 6. Respect for human rights

Original Text

1. States Parties shall ensure that the implementation of their obligations under this Convention is consistent with their obligations under international human rights law.
2. Nothing in this Convention shall be interpreted as permitting suppression of human rights or fundamental freedoms, including the rights related to freedom of expression, conscience, opinion, religion or belief, peaceful assembly and association, in accordance with applicable international human rights law.

Description

Article 6 underscores the importance of ensuring that measures to combat cybercrime do not violate human rights. This article is fundamental to ensuring that actions taken under the convention respect and protect fundamental freedoms. However, to strengthen its impact, some additional recommendations can be considered.

Recommendations

1. **Incorporate Oversight and Evaluation Mechanisms:** It is suggested to establish independent oversight and evaluation mechanisms to ensure that measures adopted under the convention align with international human rights standards. This could include the creation of a human rights oversight committee that periodically reports on compliance and potential violations (Meier et al., 2020; Ali et al., 2022).
2. **Promote Transparency and Civil Society Participation:** To strengthen human rights protection, it is advisable to promote transparency in the application of measures and encourage the participation of civil society organizations in

policy review. This will ensure that the voices of affected groups are heard and considered (Montal & Pauselli, 2023).

3. **Implementation of Human Rights Training Programs:** It is recommended to implement human rights training programs for officials responsible for enforcing the convention's measures. This will ensure they fully understand the implications of their actions on human rights and act accordingly (Cross, 2017).

Article 7. Illegal access

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish as a criminal offence under its domestic law, when committed intentionally, the access to the whole or any part of an information and communications technology system without right. [agreed ad referendum]

2. A State Party may require that the offence be committed by infringing security measures, with the intent of obtaining electronic data or other dishonest or criminal intent or in relation to an information and communications technology system that is connected to another information and communications technology system.

Description

Article 7 addresses the criminalization of unauthorized access to information and communication technology (ICT) systems. This provision is essential to protect the integrity and confidentiality of electronic data. However, some additional recommendations can be considered to strengthen its application.

Recommendations

1. **Specify Types of Unauthorized Access:** To avoid ambiguities, it is recommended to specify different types of unauthorized access, including physical and remote access, as well as the misuse of access credentials. This will ensure a clear and uniform understanding of the scope of criminalization (Gunarto et al., 2023).
2. **Include Preventive and Educational Measures:** In addition to criminalization, it is suggested to include provisions on preventive measures and educational programs to raise societal awareness about the importance of ICT security. This can help prevent incidents of unauthorized access (Krastev, 2022).
3. **Establish Proportional Sanctions:** It is crucial that sanctions for illegal access are proportional to the severity of the offense. This can include variable

penalties depending on the harm caused or the intent behind the unauthorized access, ensuring a fair and equitable application of the law (Szongoth & Vetter, 2018).

Article 8. Illegal interception

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish as criminal offences under its domestic law, when committed intentionally and without right, the interception, made by technical means, of non-public transmissions of electronic data to, from or within an information and communications technology system, including electromagnetic emissions from an information and communications technology system carrying such electronic data. [agreed ad referendum]

2. A State Party may require that the offence be committed with dishonest or criminal intent, or in relation to an information and communications technology system that is connected to another information and communications technology system

Description

Article 8 addresses the illegal interception of electronic data, one of the most severe forms of intrusion into privacy and communication security. To reinforce this article, some additional recommendations can be considered.

Recommendations

1. **Specify Types of Transmissions:** For greater clarity, it is suggested to specify the types of transmissions that are protected, such as Internet communications, mobile telephony, and other forms of data transmission. This can help avoid ambiguous interpretations and ensure broad protection (Ruslan, 2023).
2. **Include Legal Exceptions:** It is important to include clear and specific legal exceptions, such as interceptions authorized by court order in legitimate investigations. This can help balance security and privacy with law enforcement needs (Bunga, 2019).
3. **Establish Oversight and Control Mechanisms:** It is recommended to implement oversight and control mechanisms to ensure that any authorized data interception is conducted legally and ethically, and that the rights of affected individuals are respected (Lim, 2007).

Article 9. Interference with electronic data

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish as criminal offences under its domestic law, when committed intentionally and without right, the damaging, deletion, deterioration, alteration or suppression of electronic data. [agreed in informals]
2. A State Party may require that the conduct described in paragraph 1 of this article result in serious harm. [agreed ad referendum]

Description

Article 9 focuses on protecting the integrity of electronic data against unauthorized alterations. This is crucial for maintaining the reliability and security of information in information and communication technology (ICT) systems. However, to strengthen the application of this article, some additional recommendations can be considered.

Recommendations

Clarification of Terms and Scope: It is important to clearly define the terms "alteration," "damage," "deletion," "deterioration," "suppression," and "impediment of access" to avoid ambiguous interpretations and ensure uniform application of the article (Ali et al., 2022).

Include Preventive and Restorative Measures: In addition to criminalization, it is suggested to include provisions for preventive and restorative measures. This could involve implementing robust data security policies and disaster recovery plans (Kagita et al., 2020).

Establish Rapid Response Protocols: The creation of rapid response protocols for incidents of electronic data interference is recommended. This can help minimize the impact of such incidents and ensure the quick and effective restoration of compromised data (Interpol, 2022).

Article 10. Interference with an information and communications technology system

[agreed ad referendum]

Original Text

Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish as criminal offences under its domestic law, when committed intentionally and without right, the serious hindering of the

functioning of an information and communications technology system by inputting, transmitting, damaging, deleting, deteriorating, altering or suppressing electronic data.

Description

Article 10 addresses interference with the functioning of information and communication technology (ICT) systems. Such interference can have serious consequences for the security and operability of critical infrastructures. To strengthen this article, some additional recommendations can be considered.

Recommendations

1. **Clearly Define the Scope of Interference:** It is important to clearly define what constitutes "serious interference" to avoid ambiguous interpretations. This could include specific examples of acts that would be considered interference, such as denial of service (DDoS) attacks (Aldridge et al., 2017).
2. **Include Preventive and Mitigation Measures:** In addition to criminalization, it is suggested to include preventive and mitigation measures, such as the implementation of intrusion detection and prevention systems, as well as incident response plans to minimize the impact of such interference (Kagita et al., 2020).
3. **Establish International Cooperation:** Given the global nature of ICT, it is crucial to promote international cooperation to address cross-border threats. This can include agreements for information sharing and coordination of actions between countries (Grauer, 2022).

Article 11. Misuse of devices

Original Text

[agreed ad referendum] 1. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish as criminal offences under its domestic law, when committed intentionally and without right: (a) The obtaining, production, sale, procurement for use, import, distribution or otherwise making available of: (i) A device, including a program designed or adapted primarily for the purpose of committing any of the offences established in accordance with articles 7 to 10 of this Convention; or (ii) A password, access credentials, electronic signature or similar data by which the whole or any part of an information and communications technology system is capable of being accessed; with the intent that the device, including a program, password, access credentials, electronic signature, or similar data be used for the purpose of committing any of the offences established in

accordance with articles 7 to 10 of this Convention; and (b) The possession of an item referred to in paragraph 1 (a) (i) or (ii) of this article, with intent that it be used for the purpose of committing any of the offences established in accordance with articles 7 to 10 of this Convention.

2. This article shall not be interpreted as imposing criminal liability where the obtaining, production, sale, procurement for use, import, distribution or otherwise making available, or the possession referred to in paragraph 1 of this article is not for the purpose of committing an offence established in accordance with articles 7 to 10 of this Convention, such as for the authorized testing or protection of an information and communications technology system.

3. Each State Party may reserve the right not to apply paragraph 1 of this article, provided that the reservation does not concern the sale, distribution or otherwise making available of the items referred to in paragraph 1 (a) (ii) of this article.

Description

Article 11 addresses the misuse of devices and tools that can facilitate the commission of cybercrimes. This provision is crucial to prevent unauthorized access and the malicious use of technologies. However, to ensure effective implementation, some additional recommendations can be considered.

Recommendations

1. **Specify and Update Lists of Devices and Tools:** It is suggested that the lists of devices and tools specified in the article be updated periodically to include new technologies and emerging methods used in cybercrime. This can be managed by a specialized technical committee (Kagita et al., 2020).
2. **Include Exceptions for Legitimate Investigations:** It is important to include clear exceptions for the use of these tools in legitimate investigations by authorized authorities and research entities. This can help balance security with the need to conduct forensic and security investigations (Geldenhuys, 2021).
3. **Promote Education and Awareness:** In addition to criminalization, it is recommended to implement education and awareness programs to inform the public about the risks and responsibilities associated with the use of these devices and tools. This can help prevent misuse and promote safe practices (ECPAT International, 2016).

4. Establish and Implement Institutions in Each State:

Create and implement institutions in each State with the purpose of analyzing and monitoring these cases and potential crimes related to the misuse of ICTs.

Article 12. Information and communications technology system-related forgery

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish as criminal offences under its domestic law, when committed intentionally and without right, the input, alteration, deletion or suppression of electronic data resulting in inauthentic data with the intent that they be considered or acted upon for legal purposes as if they were authentic, regardless of whether or not the data are directly readable and intelligible. [agreed ad referendum]

2. A State Party may require an intent to defraud, or a similar dishonest or criminal intent, before criminal liability attaches.

Description

Article 12 focuses on the falsification of electronic data and documents, a crime that can have serious consequences in terms of trust and security in information and communication technology (ICT) systems. This article is fundamental for maintaining the integrity and validity of digital information.

Recommendations

1. **Clearly Define the Scope of Falsification:** It is important to precisely define what constitutes "falsification" in the context of electronic data and documents. This includes the creation, modification, or alteration of information with the intent to deceive (Kaur, 2021).
2. **Include Examples of Falsification:** Providing specific examples of acts of falsification can help clarify and prevent these actions. Examples could include the falsification of digital signatures, alteration of electronic medical records, and modification of digital contracts (Ajoy, 2022).
3. **Implement Verification and Authenticity Systems:** It is suggested to implement robust systems for verification and authenticity of electronic data and documents. This can include the use of blockchain technologies and advanced digital signatures to ensure the integrity of the information (Varshney et al., 2020).

Artículo 13. Robo o fraude relacionado con sistemas de tecnologías de la información y las comunicaciones

Original Text

Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish as a criminal offence under its domestic law, when committed intentionally and without right, the causing of a loss of property to another person by means of: [agreed ad referendum]

(a) Any input, alteration, deletion or suppression of electronic data; [agreed in informals]

(b) Any interference with the functioning of an information and communications technology system; [agreed ad referendum]

(c) Any deception as to factual circumstances made through an information and communications technology system that causes a person to do or omit to do anything which that person would not otherwise do or omit to do; [agreed ad referendum]

with the fraudulent or dishonest intent of procuring for oneself or for another person, without right, a gain in money or other property.

Description

Article 13 suggests that each State Party should implement laws to criminalize intentional fraudulent actions aimed at obtaining economic or other benefits for oneself or others. These actions include the alteration or deletion of electronic data, interference with information and communication systems, and deception through such systems to induce someone to act in a certain way.

Recommendations

- 1. Update Legislation:** It is suggested to adopt international standards, such as those of the Budapest Convention, to align standards and facilitate global cooperation. Additionally, consultations with experts and stakeholders can help propose robust laws with clear definitions and appropriate sanctions (Wicki-Birchler, 2020).
- 2. Develop Technological Infrastructure:** Strengthening technological infrastructure is crucial for detecting and effectively responding to

cybercrimes. Without monitoring systems and early warning mechanisms, crimes can go unnoticed or be discovered too late, causing greater harm (Holt, 2018).

- 3. Training and Awareness:** Training judges, prosecutors, and law enforcement officers is essential to ensure that cybercrimes are properly handled within the judicial system. Additionally, public awareness campaigns can help prevent these crimes by informing citizens about the risks and protection measures (UNODC, 2021).

Article 14. Offences related to online child sexual abuse or child sexual exploitation material

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish as criminal offences under its domestic law, when committed intentionally and without right, the following conduct: (a) Producing, offering, selling, distributing, transmitting, broadcasting, displaying, publishing or otherwise making available child sexual abuse or child sexual exploitation material through an information and communications technology system; (b) Soliciting, procuring or accessing child sexual abuse or child sexual exploitation material through an information and communications technology system; (c) Possessing or controlling child sexual abuse or child sexual exploitation material stored in an information and communications technology system or another storage medium; (d) Financing the offences established in accordance with subparagraphs (a) to (c) of this paragraph, which States Parties may establish as a separate offence.

2. For the purposes of this article, the term “child sexual abuse or child sexual exploitation material” shall include visual material, and may include written or audio content, that depicts, describes or represents any person under 18 years of age: (a) Engaging in real or simulated sexual activity; (b) In the presence of a person engaging in any sexual activity; (c) Whose sexual parts are displayed for primarily sexual purposes; or (d) Subjected to torture or cruel, inhumane or degrading treatment or punishment and such material is sexual in nature

3. A State Party may require that the material identified in paragraph 2 of this article be limited to material that: (a) Depicts, describes or represents a real child; or (b) Visually depicts child sexual abuse or child sexual exploitation.

4. States Parties may take steps to exclude the criminalization of: (a) Children for self-generated material depicting them as described in paragraph 2 of this article; or (b) Conduct set forth in paragraph 1 of this article, relating to material described in paragraph 2 (a) to (c) of this article, where such material is produced as part of a consensual sexual relationship, as determined by domestic law and consistent with applicable international obligations, and is maintained exclusively for the private and consensual use of the persons involved.

5. Nothing in this Convention shall affect any international obligations which are more conducive to the realization of the rights of the child.

Description

Article 14 is crucial for the protection of minors in the digital environment, addressing various aspects of online child sexual abuse. The clarity and specificity of this article are essential for its effectiveness in combating this serious crime. However, some additional recommendations can be considered to strengthen its application.

Recommendations

1. **Clearly Define "Child Sexual Abuse Material":** It is suggested to provide a clear and precise definition of "child sexual abuse material" to avoid any ambiguity and ensure a uniform interpretation. This can include a detailed description of what constitutes such material (Interpol, 2022).
2. **Include Preventive and Educational Measures:** In addition to criminalization, it is crucial to include preventive measures and educational programs to raise awareness about the dangers of online child sexual abuse and how to protect minors. This can include public awareness campaigns and training for parents and educators (ECPAT International, 2016).
3. **Promote International Cooperation:** Given the global nature of cybercrime, it is essential to promote international cooperation to combat online child sexual abuse. This can include agreements for information sharing and coordination of actions between countries (Aulia, 2023).

Article 15. Solicitation or grooming for the purpose of committing a sexual offence against a child

Original Text

[agreed ad referendum]

1. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish as criminal offences under its domestic law the act of intentionally communicating, soliciting, grooming, or making any arrangement through an information and communications technology system for the purpose of committing a sexual offence against a child, as defined in domestic law, including for the commission of any of the offences established in accordance with article 14 of this Convention.

2. A State Party may require an act in furtherance of the conduct described in paragraph 1 of this article. 3. A State Party may consider extending criminalization in accordance with paragraph 1 of this article in relation to a person believed to be a child. 4. States Parties may take steps to exclude the criminalization of children for conduct described in paragraph 1 of this article.

Description

Article 15 focuses on the criminalization of solicitation and harassment of minors for sexual abuse. This is a critical aspect of online child protection and is fundamental to preventing sexual offenses against minors. However, to enhance the effectiveness of this article, some additional recommendations can be considered.

Recommendations

Clearly Define "Solicitation" and "Harassment": It is essential to clearly define the terms "solicitation" and "harassment" to avoid ambiguous interpretations. This would include specific examples and a description of the behaviors that constitute these acts (Irawan et al., 2022).

Implement Detection and Prevention Technologies: The use of advanced technologies for the detection and prevention of online solicitation and harassment is recommended. This can include artificial intelligence systems that monitor and detect suspicious behavior patterns (Cross, 2017).

Establish Support and Rehabilitation Programs for Victims: In addition to criminalization, it is crucial to provide support and rehabilitation to the victims of solicitation and harassment, as well as their families. This can include counseling services, helplines, and rehabilitation programs to assist the affected minors (Bunga & Hiariej, 2019).

Article 16. Non-consensual dissemination of intimate images

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish as criminal offences under its domestic law, when committed intentionally and without right, the selling, distributing, transmitting, publishing or otherwise making available of an intimate image of a person by means of an information and communications technology system, without the consent of the person depicted in the image.

2. For the purpose of paragraph 1 of this article, "intimate image" shall mean a visual recording of a person over the age of 18 years made by any means, including a photograph or video recording, that is sexual in nature, in which the person's sexual parts are exposed or the person is engaged in sexual activity, which was private at the time of the recording, and in respect of which the person or persons depicted maintained a reasonable expectation of privacy at the time of the offence.

3. A State Party may extend the definition of intimate images, as appropriate, to depictions of persons who are under the age of 18 years if they are of legal age to engage in sexual activity under domestic law and the image does not depict child abuse or exploitation.

4. For the purposes of this article, a person who is under the age of 18 years and depicted in an intimate image cannot consent to the dissemination of an intimate image that constitutes child sexual abuse or child sexual exploitation material under article 14 of this Convention.

5. A State Party may require the intent to cause harm before criminal liability attaches.

Description

Article 16 addresses a growing problem in the digital age: the non-consensual dissemination of intimate images, also known as "non-consensual pornography" or "revenge porn." This provision is essential to protect the privacy and dignity of affected individuals. However, some additional recommendations can be considered to strengthen its application.

Recommendations

1. **Clearly Define "Intimate Images":** It is crucial to clearly define what constitutes "intimate images" to avoid ambiguous interpretations. This can

include any image or video that depicts nudity, explicit sexual activity, or any content that the person reasonably expects to remain private (Citron & Franks, 2014).

2. **Include Victim Support Measures:** In addition to criminalization, it is suggested to implement support measures for victims, such as counseling services, rapid removal of content from digital platforms, and legal assistance. This can help victims regain their privacy and dignity (McGlynn & Rackley, 2017).
3. **Promote Public Education and Awareness:** It is recommended to carry out public education and awareness campaigns to inform about the risks and legal consequences of non-consensual dissemination of intimate images. This can help prevent these acts and protect potential victims (Henry et al., 2020).
4. **Include a Section on AI-Modified Intimate Images:** It is important to address the issue of AI-modified intimate images of real individuals that have been altered with technology. This should be explicitly included to ensure comprehensive protection against all forms of non-consensual image dissemination.

Article 17. Laundering of proceeds of crime

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall adopt, in accordance with fundamental principles of its domestic law, such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish as criminal offences, when committed intentionally: (a) (i) The conversion or transfer of property, knowing that such property is the proceeds of crime, for the purpose of concealing or disguising the illicit origin of the property or of helping any person who is involved in the commission of the predicate offence to evade the legal consequences of that person's actions; (ii) The concealment or disguise of the true nature, source, location, disposition, movement or ownership of or rights with respect to property, knowing that such property is the proceeds of crime; (b) Subject to the basic concepts of its legal system: (i) The acquisition, possession or use of property, knowing, at the time of receipt, that such property is the proceeds of crime; (ii) Participation in, association with or conspiracy to commit, attempts to commit and aiding, abetting, facilitating and counselling the commission of any of the offences established in accordance with this article. [agreed ad referendum]

2. For purposes of implementing or applying paragraph 1 of this article: (a) Each State Party shall establish as predicate offences relevant offences established in accordance with articles 7 to 16 of this Convention; (b) In the case of States Parties whose legislation sets out a list of specific predicate offences, they shall, at a minimum, include in that list a comprehensive range of offences established in accordance with articles 7 to 16 of this Convention; (c) For the purposes of subparagraph (b) of this paragraph, predicate offences shall include offences committed both within and outside the jurisdiction of the State Party in question. However, offences committed outside the jurisdiction of a State Party shall constitute predicate offences only when the relevant conduct is a criminal offence under the domestic law of the State where it is committed and would be a criminal offence under the domestic law of the State Party implementing or applying this article, had it been committed there; [agreed ad referendum] (d) Each State Party shall furnish copies of its laws that give effect to this article and of any subsequent changes to such laws or a description thereof to the Secretary-General of the United Nations; [agreed ad referendum] (e) If required by fundamental principles of the domestic law of a State Party, it may be provided that the offences set forth in paragraph 1 of this article do not apply to the persons who committed the predicate offence; [agreed ad referendum] (f) Knowledge, intent or purpose required as an element of an offence set forth in paragraph 1 of this article may be inferred from objective factual circumstances. [agreed ad referendum]

Description

Article 17 focuses on combating money laundering derived from criminal activities, a critical component for dismantling the financial operations of organized and cybercrime. This article is essential to ensure that crime proceeds cannot be easily integrated into the legal economy.

Recommendations

Expand Definitions of "Crime Proceeds": It is important to clearly define what is meant by "crime proceeds" to include not only tangible goods but also digital assets and cryptocurrencies, which are increasingly used in criminal activities (Caneppele & Aebi, 2017).

Implement Detection and Monitoring Technologies: It is recommended to utilize advanced detection and monitoring technologies to track suspicious transactions. This can include the use of artificial intelligence and big data analytics to identify unusual patterns in the movement of funds (Grauer, 2022).

Strengthen International Cooperation: Since money laundering often involves cross-border transactions, it is crucial to promote international cooperation between financial and judicial authorities to trace and recover crime proceeds. This can include signing bilateral and multilateral agreements (Krajowe Biuro, 2020).

Article 18. Liability of legal persons

[agreed ad referendum]

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall adopt such measures as may be necessary, consistent with its legal principles, to establish the liability of legal persons for participation in the offences established in accordance with this Convention.
2. Subject to the legal principles of the State Party, the liability of legal persons may be criminal, civil or administrative.
3. Such liability shall be without prejudice to the criminal liability of the natural persons who have committed the offences.
4. Each State Party shall, in particular, ensure that legal persons held liable in accordance with this article are subject to effective, proportionate and dissuasive criminal or non-criminal sanctions, including monetary sanctions.

Description

Article 18 focuses on the liability of legal entities, which is essential for addressing corporate complicity in cybercrimes. This approach ensures that corporate entities cannot evade responsibility for criminal activities facilitated by their structures.

Recommendations

Specify the Scope of Corporate Liability: It is crucial to clearly define the scope of liability for legal entities, including the circumstances under which a company can be held accountable for inadequate supervision or control over its employees (Weber, 2009).

Include Compliance Measures and Best Practices: It is suggested to implement compliance measures and best practices that legal entities must follow to prevent cybercrimes. This can include the creation of robust internal policies, training programs, and periodic audits (Teichmann & Wittmann, 2022).

Establish Proportional and Effective Sanctions: It is important that sanctions for legal entities are proportional to the severity of the crime and effective in deterring future offenses. This can include significant fines, commercial restrictions, and the obligation to implement corrective measures (Khan et al., 2022).

Article 19. Participation and attempt

Original Text

[agreed ad referendum]

1. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish as a criminal offence, in accordance with its domestic law, when committed intentionally, the participation in any capacity, such as that of an accomplice, assistant or instigator, in an offence established in accordance with this Convention.

2. Each State Party may adopt the necessary legislative and other measures to establish as a criminal offence, in accordance with its domestic law, when committed intentionally, any attempt to commit an offence established in accordance with this Convention.

3. Each State Party may adopt the necessary legislative and other measures to establish as a criminal offence, in accordance with its domestic law, when committed intentionally, the preparation for an offence established in accordance with this Convention.

Description

Article 19 addresses the importance of criminalizing participation and attempts in cybercrime acts. It is crucial to consider not only direct action but also preparatory and complicity acts, which are fundamental for a comprehensive strategy to prevent and combat cybercrime.

Recommendations

Criminalization of Preparatory and Complicity Acts: It is recommended that legislative measures include clear and detailed definitions of preparatory and complicity acts to ensure there is no ambiguity in their application (Ali et al., 2022).

Focus on International Coordination: Promote collaboration among State Parties to harmonize national legislations on participation and attempts in cybercrimes, ensuring a coherent and coordinated response to cybercrime at the global level (Interpol, 2022).

Training and Awareness Programs: Implement training and awareness programs for law enforcement and judicial operators on the relevance of preparatory and complicity acts in the context of cybercrime, ensuring the effective application of laws (UNODC, 2021).

Article 20. Statute of limitations

Original Text
[agreed ad referendum]

Each State Party shall, where appropriate, considering the gravity of the crime, establish under its domestic law a long statute of limitations period in which to commence proceedings for any offence established in accordance with this Convention and establish a longer statute of limitations period or provide for the suspension of the statute of limitations where the alleged offender has evaded the administration of justice.

Description

Article 20 highlights the need to establish an adequate statute of limitations for cybercrimes, considering the severity of these crimes and the possibility that perpetrators may evade justice. A long statute of limitations is essential to ensure that those responsible for these crimes can be prosecuted, even if several years have passed since the commission of the crime.

Recommendations

Prolonged Statute of Limitations: It is recommended to establish a prolonged statute of limitations for cybercrimes due to the complexity of investigations and the difficulty of identifying and locating perpetrators. A longer period will allow authorities to gather sufficient evidence and bring those responsible to justice (Balajanov, 2018).

Suspension of the Statute of Limitations: Include clear provisions for the suspension of the statute of limitations in cases where criminals have evaded justice. This will ensure that individuals attempting to avoid prosecution do not benefit from time limitations (Nurahman, 2019).

International Cooperation and Harmonization of Laws: Promote international cooperation and the harmonization of statutes of limitations among State Parties to ensure a coordinated and effective response to cybercrimes, facilitating the capture and prosecution of criminals globally (Interpol, 2022).

Article 21. Prosecution, adjudication and sanctions

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall make the commission of an offence established in accordance with this Convention liable to effective, proportionate

and dissuasive sanctions that take into account the gravity of the offence. [agreed ad referendum]

2. Each State Party may adopt, in accordance with its domestic law, such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish aggravating circumstances in relation to the offences established in accordance with this Convention, including circumstances that affect critical information infrastructures.
3. Each State Party shall endeavour to ensure that any discretionary legal powers under its domestic law relating to the prosecution of persons for offences established in accordance with this Convention are exercised in order to maximize the effectiveness of law enforcement measures in respect of those offences and with due regard to the need to deter the commission of such offences. [agreed ad referendum]
4. Each State Party shall ensure that any person prosecuted for offences established in accordance with this Convention enjoys all rights and guarantees in conformity with domestic law and consistent with the international obligations of the State Party, including the right to a fair trial and the rights of the defence.
5. In the case of offences established in accordance with this Convention, each State Party shall take appropriate measures, in accordance with its domestic law and with due regard to the rights of the defence, to seek to ensure that conditions imposed in connection with decisions on release pending trial or appeal take into consideration the need to ensure the presence of the defendant at subsequent criminal proceedings. [agreed ad referendum]
6. Each State Party shall take into account the gravity of the offences concerned when considering the eventuality of early release or parole of persons convicted of such offences. [agreed ad referendum]
7. States Parties shall ensure that appropriate measures are in place under domestic law to protect children who are accused of offences established in accordance with this Convention, consistent with the obligations under the Convention on the Rights of the Child and the applicable Protocols thereto, as well as other applicable international or regional instruments. [agreed ad referendum]
8. Nothing contained in this Convention shall affect the principle that the description of the offences established in accordance with this Convention and of the applicable legal defences or other legal principles controlling the lawfulness of conduct is reserved to the domestic law of a State Party and that such offences shall be prosecuted and punished in accordance with that law. [agreed ad referendum]

Description

Article 21 underscores the importance of imposing effective, proportional, and dissuasive penalties for cybercrimes, while ensuring respect for the rights of the accused. Additionally, it emphasizes the need to consider aggravating circumstances and to protect children in the context of these crimes.

Recommendations

Effective and Proportional Penalties: It is crucial that penalties are effective, proportional, and dissuasive, tailored to the severity of cybercrimes to ensure justice and prevent future offenses. This includes significant fines and rehabilitation measures for offenders (Brenner & Clarke, 2009).

Aggravating Circumstances: Clearly define and specify aggravating circumstances, especially those affecting critical information infrastructures. This can include attacks on health, energy, and financial systems, which have a significant impact on national security and the economy (Agusta Ridha Minin, 2018).

Protection of the Rights of the Accused: Ensure that all accused individuals enjoy a fair trial and the rights to defense, in accordance with international human rights standards. This is fundamental to maintaining the integrity of the justice system (Holt, 2018).

Special Measures for Minors: Implement special measures for the protection of children accused of cybercrimes, in line with the Convention on the Rights of the Child and other international instruments. This includes considering alternatives to detention and ensuring appropriate judicial processes for minors (Interpol, 2022).

Article 22. Jurisdiction

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall adopt such measures as may be necessary to establish its jurisdiction over the offences established in accordance with this Convention when: (a) The offence is committed in the territory of that State Party; or [agreed ad referendum] (b) The offence is committed on board a vessel that is flying the flag of that State Party or an aircraft that is registered under the laws of that State Party at the time when the offence is committed. [agreed ad referendum]
2. Subject to article 5 of this Convention, a State Party may also establish its jurisdiction over any such offence when: [agreed ad referendum] (a) The offence is committed against a national of that State Party; or [agreed ad referendum] (b) The offence is committed by a national of that State Party or a stateless person with habitual residence in its territory; or [agreed ad referendum] (c) The offence is one of those established in accordance with

- article 17, paragraph 1 (b) (ii), of this Convention and is committed outside its territory with a view to the commission of an offence established in accordance with article 17, paragraph 1 (a) (i) or (ii) or (b) (i), of this Convention within its territory; or [agreed ad referendum] (d) The offence is committed against the State Party.
3. For the purposes of article 37, paragraph 11, of this Convention, each State Party shall take such measures as may be necessary to establish its jurisdiction over the offences established in accordance with this Convention when the alleged offender is present in its territory and it does not extradite such person solely on the ground that the person is one of its nationals. [agreed ad referendum]
 4. Each State Party may also adopt such measures as may be necessary to establish its jurisdiction over the offences established in accordance with this Convention when the alleged offender is present in its territory and it does not extradite the person. [agreed ad referendum]
 5. If a State Party exercising its jurisdiction under paragraph 1 or 2 of this article has been notified, or has otherwise learned, that any other States Parties are conducting an investigation, prosecution or judicial proceeding in respect of the same conduct, the competent authorities of those States Parties shall, as appropriate, consult one another with a view to coordinating their actions. [agreed ad referendum]
 6. Without prejudice to norms of general international law, this Convention shall not exclude the exercise of any criminal jurisdiction established by a State Party in accordance with its domestic law. [agreed ad referendum]

Description

Article 22 addresses the jurisdiction of State Parties over cybercrimes, highlighting the importance of effective coordination and clear establishment of jurisdictions to ensure that crimes do not go unpunished due to legal gaps.

Recommendations

Clarification of Jurisdiction: It is fundamental that State Parties clearly define the limits and scope of their jurisdiction over cybercrimes, ensuring that national laws are consistent with international provisions. This includes jurisdiction over crimes committed outside the national territory but that directly affect the State (Arnell & Faturoti, 2023).

International Cooperation: Promoting international cooperation among State Parties is essential to address the transnational nature of cybercrimes. This can include bilateral and multilateral agreements to facilitate investigation, prosecution, and extradition of offenders (Siregar & Sinaga, 2021).

Coordination Mechanisms: Establish clear coordination mechanisms among State Parties when multiple jurisdictions are involved in the investigation or prosecution of the same crime. This can help avoid jurisdictional conflicts and ensure an efficient and coordinated response (Wingfield & Wingo, 2021).

Article 23. Scope of procedural measures

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish the powers and procedures provided for in this chapter for the purpose of specific criminal investigations or proceedings.
2. Except as provided otherwise in this Convention, each State Party shall apply the powers and procedures referred to in paragraph 1 of this article to:
(a) The criminal offences established in accordance with this Convention; (b) Other criminal offences committed by means of an information and communications technology system; and (c) The collection of evidence in electronic form of any criminal offence.
3. (a) Each State Party may reserve the right to apply the measures referred to in article 29 of this Convention only to offences or categories of offences specified in the reservation, provided that the range of such offences or categories of offences is not more restricted than the range of offences to which it applies the measures referred to in article 30 of this Convention. Each State Party shall consider restricting such a reservation to enable the broadest application of the measures referred to in article 29; (b) Where a State Party, owing to limitations in its legislation in force at the time of the adoption of this Convention, is not able to apply the measures referred to in articles 29 and 30 of this Convention to communications being transmitted with in an information and communications technology system of a service provider, which: (i) Is being operated for the benefit of a closed group of users; and (ii) Does not employ public communications networks and is not connected with another information and communications technology system, whether public or private; that State Party may reserve the right not to apply these measures to such communications. Each State Party shall consider restricting such a reservation to enable the broadest application of the measures referred to in articles 29 and 30 of this Convention.
4. States Parties shall apply, as appropriate, the powers and procedures set out in this chapter in providing relevant forms of international cooperation provided for in this Convention. Conditions and safeguards established in

accordance with article 24 of this Convention shall also apply, at the domestic level, to such powers and procedures when they are used to render international cooperation.

Description

Article 23 establishes the scope of procedural measures that State Parties must adopt to facilitate the investigation and prosecution of cybercrimes. These measures are fundamental to ensuring that criminal proceedings are effective and that electronic evidence can be properly collected.

Recommendations

Implementation of Legislative Measures: State Parties should adopt clear and specific legislative measures that allow for the effective implementation of the powers and procedures necessary for the investigation and prosecution of cybercrimes (Curtis & Oxburgh, 2023).

Broad Application of Procedural Measures: It is recommended that State Parties consider minimizing reservations to allow the broadest possible application of the procedural measures mentioned in Articles 29 and 30. This is crucial to ensure that investigations and prosecutions are comprehensive and effective (Ahsan et al., 2022).

International Cooperation: Promoting international cooperation is essential to address the transnational nature of cybercrimes. State Parties should establish effective cooperation mechanisms and ensure that the conditions and safeguards for international cooperation are applied consistently (Klevtsov, 2020).

Article 24. Conditions and safeguards

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall ensure that the establishment, implementation and application of the powers and procedures provided for in this chapter are subject to conditions and safeguards provided for under its domestic law, which shall provide for the protection of human rights, in accordance with its obligations under international human rights law, and which shall incorporate the principle of proportionality.

2. In accordance with and pursuant to the domestic law of each State Party, such conditions and safeguards shall, as appropriate in view of the nature of the procedure or power concerned, include, inter alia, judicial or other independent review, the right to an effective remedy, grounds justifying

application, and limitation of the scope and the duration of such power or procedure.

3. To the extent that it is consistent with the public interest, in particular the proper administration of justice, each State Party shall consider the impact of the powers and procedures in this chapter upon the rights, responsibilities and legitimate interests of third parties.

Description

Article 24 establishes the conditions, procedures, and security responsibilities that the State will implement to protect human rights. These guidelines are essential to ensure human rights protection and will include judicial or independent review, the right to an effective remedy, and justification and limitation of the duration of these powers.

Recommendations

Ensure Transparency and Accountability: It is recommended that State Parties implement transparent and accountable mechanisms for overseeing the powers and procedures provided in this chapter. This could include the publication of periodic reports on the use of these powers and procedures, as well as independent audits to assess their compliance with human rights (Bamberger & Mulligan, 2015).

Incorporate Civil Society Oversight: Including the participation of civil society organizations in the review and oversight of the measures adopted can strengthen the protection of human rights. Organizations can act as independent observers and provide recommendations to improve current policies and practices (Schwartz & Solove, 2014).

Develop Training Protocols for Officials: Ensure that officials responsible for implementing these powers and procedures receive adequate training on human rights and the principle of proportionality. Training should include practical scenarios and case studies to ensure a comprehensive understanding and proper application of safeguards (Curtis & Oxburgh, 2023).

Human Rights Impact Assessment: Before the implementation of any new power or procedure, a human rights impact assessment should be conducted to identify potential risks and mitigate negative impacts. This assessment should be a standard practice to ensure that measures do not violate fundamental rights (Ali et al., 2022).

Article 25. Expedited preservation of stored electronic data

Original Text

[agreed ad referendum]

1. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to enable its competent authorities to order or similarly obtain the expeditious preservation of specified electronic data, including traffic data, content data and subscriber information, that have been stored by means of an information and communications technology system, in particular where there are grounds to believe that the electronic data are particularly vulnerable to loss or modification.
2. Where a State Party gives effect to paragraph 1 of this article by means of an order to a person to preserve specified stored electronic data in the person's possession or control, the State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to oblige that person to preserve and maintain the integrity of those electronic data for a period of time as long as necessary, up to a maximum of 90 days, to enable the competent authorities to seek their disclosure. A State Party may provide for such an order to be subsequently renewed.
3. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to oblige the custodian or other person who is to preserve the electronic data to keep confidential the undertaking of such procedures for the period of time provided for in its domestic legislation.

Description

Article 25 focuses on the expedited preservation of stored electronic data, highlighting the importance of ensuring that such data, including traffic data, content data, and subscriber information, is quickly preserved to prevent its loss or modification. This article is fundamental for criminal investigations, where the integrity and availability of electronic data are crucial.

Recommendations

Implementation of Clear Legislative Measures: State Parties should adopt clear legislative measures that specify the procedures and requirements for the expedited preservation of electronic data. These measures should include guidelines on how to issue preservation orders and the obligations of data custodians (Curtis & Oxburgh, 2023).

Retention Period and Renewal: It is crucial to clearly define the retention period for data, which should be sufficient to allow the competent authorities to gather evidence. The possibility of renewing the preservation order should be considered to ensure that the data is available throughout the entire investigation (Siregar & Sinaga, 2021).

Confidentiality of Preservation Orders: Include measures to ensure the confidentiality of preservation orders to prevent suspects from altering or destroying data. Legislation should establish penalties for those who fail to comply with these confidentiality obligations (Dragomir, 2022).

Article 26. Expedited preservation and partial disclosure of traffic data

[agreed ad referendum]

Original Text

Each State Party shall adopt, in respect of traffic data that are to be preserved under the provisions of article 25 of this Convention, such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to: (a) Ensure that such expeditious preservation of traffic data is available regardless of whether one or more service providers were involved in the transmission of a communication; and (b) Ensure the expeditious disclosure to the State Party's competent authority, or a person designated by that authority, of a sufficient amount of traffic data to enable the State Party to identify the service providers and the path through which the communication or indicated information was transmitted.

Description

Article 26 addresses the expedited preservation and partial disclosure of traffic data, emphasizing the importance of preserving and quickly disclosing these data regardless of the number of service providers involved. This provision is crucial to ensure the continuity and effectiveness of criminal investigations.

Recommendations

1. **Legislation for Expedited Preservation:** State Parties should adopt legislative measures to ensure the expedited preservation of traffic data, even when multiple service providers are involved. This will ensure that there are no gaps in the collection of essential evidence (Wicki-Birchler, 2020).
2. **Rapid Disclosure of Data:** Implement clear procedures for the rapid disclosure of traffic data to competent authorities. The legislation should specify the timeframes and conditions under which service providers must provide these data (Saxena, 2023).

- 3. Identification of Service Providers:** Ensure that national laws allow for the rapid identification of all service providers involved in data transmission. This is crucial for tracing the source of communications and facilitating the investigation (Wicki-Birchler, 2020).

Article 27. Production order

Original Text
[agreed ad referendum]

Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to empower its competent authorities to order: (a) A person in its territory to submit specified electronic data in that person's possession or control that are stored in an information and communications technology system or an electronic data storage medium; and (b) A service provider offering its services in the territory of the State Party to submit subscriber information relating to such services in that service provider's possession or control.

Description

Article 27 addresses the issuance of production orders, which allow competent authorities to request specific electronic data from individuals and service providers. This mechanism is essential for obtaining crucial information during criminal investigations.

Recommendations

- 1. Implementation of Clear Legislative Measures:** State Parties should adopt clear legislative measures that specify the procedures and requirements for issuing production orders. These measures should ensure that competent authorities have the power to request necessary electronic data for investigations (Curtis & Oxburgh, 2023).
- 2. Protection of Personal Data:** It is essential to include adequate safeguards to protect the privacy and rights of individuals when production orders are issued. The legislation should balance the need to obtain data for investigations with the protection of personal data (Wicki-Birchler, 2020).
- 3. Collaboration with Service Providers:** Encouraging collaboration between competent authorities and service providers is crucial. Service providers should be legally obligated to comply with production orders promptly and accurately (Saxena, 2023).

Article 28. Search and seizure of stored electronic data

Original Text

[agreed ad referendum]

1. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to empower its competent authorities to search or similarly access: (a) An information and communications technology system, part of it, and electronic data stored therein; and (b) An electronic data storage medium in which the electronic data sought may be stored; in the territory of that State Party.

2. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to ensure that, where its authorities search or similarly access a specific information and communications technology system or part of it, pursuant to paragraph 1 (a) of this article, and have grounds to believe that the electronic data sought are stored in another information and communications technology system or part of it in its territory, and such data are lawfully accessible from or available to the initial system, such authorities shall be able to expeditiously conduct the search to obtain access to that other information and communications technology system.

3. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to empower its competent authorities to seize or similarly secure electronic data in its territory accessed in accordance with paragraph 1 or 2 of this article. These measures shall include the power to: (a) Seize or similarly secure an information and communications technology system or part of it, or an electronic data storage medium; (b) Make and retain copies of those electronic data in electronic form; (c) Maintain the integrity of the relevant stored electronic data; (d) Render inaccessible or remove those electronic data in the accessed information and communications technology system.

4. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to empower its competent authorities to order any person who has knowledge about the functioning of the information and communications technology system in question, the information and telecommunications network, or their component parts, or measures applied to protect the electronic data therein, to provide, as is reasonable, the necessary information to enable the undertaking of the measures referred to in paragraphs 1 to 3 of this article.

Description

Article 28 addresses the search and seizure of stored electronic data, an essential tool for criminal investigations in the digital age. The ability to access, secure, and maintain the integrity of electronic data is crucial for the success of these investigations.

Recommendations

Legislation for Search and Seizure: State Parties should implement clear legislative measures that specify the procedures for the search and seizure of electronic data. These laws must ensure that competent authorities can act efficiently and within the established legal framework (Curtis & Oxburgh, 2023).

Integrity and Security of Data: It is essential that legislative measures include provisions to maintain the integrity and security of electronic data during and after its seizure. This is crucial to preserve evidence and ensure its validity in judicial proceedings (Wicki-Birchler, 2020).

Collaboration and Technical Expertise: Encouraging collaboration with experts in information technology and telecommunications is vital. Competent authorities should have access to individuals with specialized knowledge who can provide the necessary technical information to conduct effective searches and seizures (Saxena, 2023).

Article 29. Real-time collection of traffic data

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to empower its competent authorities to: (a) Collect or record, through the application of technical means in the territory of that State Party; and (b) Compel a service provider, within its existing technical capability: (i) To collect or record, through the application of technical means in the territory of that State Party; or (ii) To cooperate and assist the competent authorities in the collection or recording of; traffic data, in real time, associated with specified communications in its territory transmitted by means of an information and communications technology system.

2. Where a State Party, owing to the principles of its domestic legal system, cannot adopt the measures referred to in paragraph 1 (a) of this article, it may instead adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to ensure the real-time collection or recording of traffic data associated with

specified communications transmitted in its territory, through the application of technical means in that territory.

3. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to oblige a service provider to keep confidential the fact of the execution of any power provided for in this article and any information relating to it.

Description

Article 29 addresses the real-time collection of traffic data, an essential tool for surveillance and the prevention of cybercrime. The ability of competent authorities to collect these data in real-time is crucial for detecting and preventing online criminal activities.

Recommendations

Implementation of Clear Legislative Measures: State Parties should adopt clear legislative measures that specify the procedures and requirements for the real-time collection of traffic data. These measures should ensure that competent authorities have the power to act efficiently and within the established legal framework (Feldle, 2020).

Technical Capacity of Service Providers: It is essential that laws require service providers to fully cooperate with competent authorities and maintain the technical capability to collect and record traffic data in real-time. This includes the obligation to update their systems to comply with legal requirements (Da-Yu Kao et al., 2019).

Confidentiality and Data Protection: Legislative measures should include provisions to ensure the confidentiality of real-time traffic data collection. This is crucial to protect individuals' privacy and the integrity of investigations (Saxena, 2023).

Article 30. Interception of content data

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary, in relation to a range of serious criminal offences to be determined by domestic law, to empower its competent authorities to: (a) Collect or record, through the application of technical means in the territory of that State Party; and (b) Compel a service provider, within its existing technical capability: (i) To collect or record, through the application of technical means in the territory of that State Party; or (ii) To cooperate and assist the competent authorities in the collection or recording of; content data, in real

time, of specified communications in its territory transmitted by means of an information and communications technology system.

2. Where a State Party, owing to the principles of its domestic legal system, cannot adopt the measures referred to in paragraph 1 (a) of this article, it may instead adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to ensure the real-time collection or recording of content data on specified communications in its territory, through the application of technical means in that territory.

3. Each State Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to oblige a service provider to keep confidential the fact of the execution of any power provided for in this article and any information relating to it.

Description

Article 30 focuses on the real-time interception of content data, an essential tool for preventing and detecting serious crimes. The ability of competent authorities to intercept and record content data in real-time is crucial in the fight against cybercrime.

Recommendations

Implementation of Clear Legislative Measures: State Parties should adopt clear legislative measures that specify the procedures and requirements for the interception of content data. These measures should ensure that competent authorities have the power to act efficiently and within the established legal framework (Clough, 2015).

Technical Capacity of Service Providers: It is essential that laws require service providers to fully cooperate with competent authorities and maintain the technical capability to intercept and record content data in real-time. This includes the obligation to update their systems to comply with legal requirements (Han, 2023).

Confidentiality and Data Protection: Legislative measures should include provisions to ensure the confidentiality of content data interception. This is crucial to protect individuals' privacy and the integrity of investigations (Sabu et al., 2023).

Article 31. Freezing, seizure and confiscation of the proceeds of crime

Original Text

[agreed ad referendum]

1. Each State Party shall adopt, to the greatest extent possible within its domestic legal system, such measures as may be necessary to

enable the confiscation of: (a) Proceeds of crime derived from offences established in accordance with this Convention or property the value of which corresponds to that of such proceeds; (b) Property, equipment or other instrumentalities used in or destined for use in offences established in accordance with this Convention.

2. Each State Party shall adopt such measures as may be necessary to enable the identification, tracing, freezing or seizure of any item referred to in paragraph 1 of this article for the purpose of eventual confiscation.
3. Each State Party shall adopt, in accordance with its domestic law, such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to regulate the administration by the competent authorities of frozen, seized or confiscated property covered in paragraphs 1 and 2 of this article.
4. If proceeds of crime have been transformed or converted, in part or in full, into other property, such property shall be liable to the measures referred to in this article instead of the proceeds.
5. If proceeds of crime have been intermingled with property acquired from legitimate sources, such property shall, without prejudice to any powers relating to freezing or seizure, be liable to confiscation up to the assessed value of the intermingled proceeds.
6. Income or other benefits derived from proceeds of crime, from property into which proceeds of crime have been transformed or converted or from property with which proceeds of crime have been intermingled, shall also be liable to the measures referred to in this article, in the same manner and to the same extent as proceeds of crime.
7. For the purposes of this article and article 50 of this Convention, each State Party shall empower its courts or other competent authorities to order that bank, financial or commercial records be made available or be seized. A State Party shall not decline to act under the provisions of this paragraph on the ground of bank secrecy.
8. Each State Party may consider the possibility of requiring that an offender demonstrate the lawful origin of alleged proceeds of crime or other property liable to confiscation, to the extent that such a requirement is consistent with the principles of their domestic law and with the nature of the judicial and other proceedings.
9. The provisions of this article shall not be construed as prejudicing the rights of bona fide third parties.
10. Nothing contained in this article shall affect the principle that the measures to which it refers shall be defined and implemented in accordance with the provisions of the domestic law of a State Party.

Description

Article 31 focuses on the freezing, seizure, and confiscation of proceeds of crime, a crucial aspect for dismantling criminal operations and deterring the commission of cybercrimes. The ability of authorities to track, seize, and manage these assets is essential for the effective fight against cybercrime.

Recommendations

Legislative Measures for Confiscation: State Parties should implement clear legislative measures that allow for the confiscation of proceeds of crime and assets used in the commission of cybercrimes. This should include the ability to confiscate assets whose value corresponds to that of the proceeds of crime (Setiawahyudi, 2015).

Identification and Tracking of Assets: It is essential that authorities have the legal and technical tools necessary to identify, track, and freeze assets related to cybercrimes. International cooperation and information sharing are crucial in this process (Snail, 2009).

Management of Confiscated Assets: State Parties should establish clear procedures for the management of frozen, seized, or confiscated assets. This includes preserving their value and ensuring their proper final disposition (Rajaan & Dadhich, 2020).

Article 32. Establishment of criminal record

Original Text

[agreed ad referendum]

Each State Party may adopt such legislative or other measures as may be necessary to take into consideration, under such terms as, and for the purpose that, it deems appropriate, any previous conviction in another State of an alleged offender for the purpose of using such information in criminal proceedings relating to an offence established in accordance with this Convention.

Description

Article 32 addresses the consideration of previous convictions in other States in criminal proceedings. This is essential to ensure that an individual's criminal history is appropriately considered, which can influence judicial decisions and the punitive measures applied.

Recommendations

Adoption of Legislative Measures: State Parties should adopt legislative measures that allow the consideration of previous convictions from other States in national criminal proceedings. This is crucial to ensure that criminal histories are properly evaluated and informed decisions are made in criminal cases (Tiutiuhin, 2022).

International Cooperation: It is fundamental to establish mechanisms of international cooperation that facilitate the exchange of information on previous convictions between States. This includes implementing systems and protocols that ensure the accurate and timely transmission of this information (Spratt, 2006).

Protection of the Rights of the Accused: Legislative measures should include safeguards to protect the rights of the accused, ensuring that information on previous convictions is used fairly and does not cause undue prejudice. This is essential to maintain the integrity of the judicial process (Papai-Tarr, 2020).

Article 33. Protection of witnesses

[agreed ad referendum]

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall take appropriate measures, in accordance with its domestic law and within its means, to provide effective protection from potential retaliation or intimidation for witnesses who give testimony or, in good faith and on reasonable grounds, provide information concerning offences established in accordance with this Convention or otherwise cooperate with investigative or judicial authorities and, as appropriate, for their relatives and other persons close to them.
2. The measures envisaged in paragraph 1 of this article may include, inter alia, without prejudice to the rights of the defendant, including the right to due process: (a) Establishing procedures for the physical protection of such persons, such as, to the extent necessary and feasible, relocating them and permitting, where appropriate, non-disclosure or limitations on the disclosure of information concerning the identity and whereabouts of such persons; (b) Providing evidentiary rules to permit witness testimony to be given in a manner that ensures the safety of the witness, such as permitting testimony to be given through the use of communications technology such as video links or other adequate means.

3. States Parties shall consider entering into agreements or arrangements with other States for the relocation of persons referred to in paragraph 1 of this article.

4. The provisions of this article shall also apply to victims insofar as they are witnesses.

Description

Article 33 establishes measures to protect the integrity of witnesses who provide information about the crimes covered by this convention. It sets forth the procedures and standards to physically protect individuals when they present their testimony.

Recommendations

1. **Protection Against Retaliation or Intimidation:** Create and strengthen laws in State Parties to protect witnesses and whistleblowers from retaliation, including intimidation and harassment. Policies should define protection procedures and the scope of authorities in safeguarding witnesses and whistleblowers (Sarkar & Shukla, 2023).
2. **Implementation of Protection Measures:** Establish specific measures such as developing witness protection programs that include physical protection or relocation as needed. Additionally, create mechanisms to prevent the disclosure of information regarding the identity and whereabouts of witnesses (Nurahman, 2020).
3. **Protection and Monitoring of Witnesses:** Apply protection measures to both victims and witnesses, providing them with psychological and legal support to enable them to testify without fear of retaliation. Furthermore, it is suggested to monitor these witnesses and whistleblowers of cybercrimes to ensure the effectiveness of the protection measures (Nurahman, 2020).

Article 34. Assistance to and protection of victims

Original Text

1. Each State Party shall take appropriate measures within its means to provide assistance and protection to victims of offences established in accordance with this Convention, in particular in cases of threat of retaliation or intimidation. [agreed ad referendum]

2. Each State Party shall, subject to its domestic law, establish appropriate procedures to provide access to compensation and restitution for victims of

offences established in accordance with this Convention.
[agreed ad referendum]

3. Each State Party shall, subject to its domestic law, enable views and concerns of victims to be presented and considered at appropriate stages of criminal proceedings against offenders in a manner not prejudicial to the rights of the defence. [agreed ad referendum]

4. With respect to the offences established in accordance with articles 14 to 16 of this Convention, each State Party shall, subject to its domestic law, take measures to provide assistance to victims of such offences, including for their physical and psychological recovery, in cooperation with relevant international organizations, non-governmental organizations, and other elements of civil society.

5. In applying the provisions of paragraphs 2 to 4 of this article, each State Party shall take into account the age, gender and the particular circumstances and needs of victims, including the particular circumstances and needs of children.

6. Each State Party shall, to the extent consistent with its domestic legal framework, take steps to ensure compliance with requests to remove or render inaccessible the content described in articles 14 and 16 of this Convention.

Description

Article 34 highlights the importance of providing assistance and protection to victims of cybercrimes, ensuring they receive adequate support, compensation, and that their voices are heard in criminal proceedings. Protecting victims, especially in cases of threats of retaliation or intimidation, is crucial to maintaining their safety and well-being.

Recommendations

Protection and Assistance Measures: State Parties should implement clear legislative measures to guarantee the assistance and protection of victims of cybercrimes. This includes creating mechanisms for psychological and physical support, as well as providing safe shelters when necessary (Mabeka & Cassim, 2023).

Access to Compensation and Restitution: It is essential to establish clear and accessible procedures for victims to obtain compensation and restitution. This includes creating specific funds to compensate victims of cybercrimes and cooperating with international and non-governmental organizations to facilitate these processes (Agung et al., 2023).

Incorporation of Victims' Opinions: Victims should have the opportunity to present their opinions and concerns during criminal proceedings, ensuring that their perspective is considered without compromising the rights of the defense. This may include implementing legal support services and providing free legal representatives for victims (Veresha, 2018).

Article 35. General principles of international cooperation

Original Text

1. States Parties shall cooperate with each other in accordance with the provisions of this Convention, as well as other applicable international instruments on international cooperation in criminal matters, and domestic laws, for the purpose of: (a) The investigation and prosecution of, and judicial proceedings in relation to, the criminal offences established in accordance with this Convention, including the freezing, seizure, confiscation and return of the proceeds from such offences; (b) The collecting, obtaining, preserving and sharing of evidence in electronic form of criminal offences established in accordance with this Convention; (c) The collecting, obtaining, preserving and sharing of evidence in electronic form of any serious crime, including serious crimes established in accordance with other applicable United Nations conventions and protocols in force at the time of the adoption of this Convention.
2. For the purpose of the collecting, obtaining, preserving and sharing of evidence in electronic form of offences as provided for in paragraph 1 (b) and (c) of this article, the relevant paragraphs of article 40, and articles 41 to 46 of this Convention shall apply.
3. In matters of international cooperation, whenever dual criminality is considered a requirement, it shall be deemed fulfilled irrespective of whether the laws of the requested State Party place the offence within the same category of offence or denominate the offence by the same terminology as the requesting State Party, if the conduct underlying the offence for which assistance is sought is a criminal offence under the laws of both States Parties.

Description

Article 35 emphasizes the importance of international cooperation in the investigation and prosecution of cybercrimes. Effective collaboration among State Parties is essential to combat cybercrime in a global and coordinated manner.

Recommendations

Strengthening International Cooperation: State Parties should strengthen international cooperation mechanisms, ensuring clear and effective protocols for collaboration in cybercrime investigations. This includes adopting measures that facilitate the rapid and secure exchange of information between competent authorities (Klevtsov, 2020).

Harmonization of Legislations: It is crucial to harmonize national legislations with international standards to ensure the coherent and effective application of measures against cybercrime. Harmonization helps overcome legal differences and facilitates cooperation between countries (Cerezo et al., 2007).

Recognition of Double Criminality: State Parties should recognize the principle of double criminality in a flexible manner, ensuring that this requirement is met as long as the underlying conduct is a crime in both State Parties, regardless of differences in classification or legal terminology (Skulysh, 2014).

Article 36. Protection of personal data

Original Text

1. (a) A State Party transferring personal data pursuant to this Convention shall do so in accordance with its domestic law and any obligations the transferring Party may have under applicable international law. States Parties shall not be required to transfer personal data in accordance with this Convention if the data cannot be provided in compliance with their applicable laws concerning the protection of personal data; (b) Where the transfer of personal data would not be compliant with paragraph 1 (a) of this article, States Parties may seek to impose appropriate conditions, in accordance with such applicable laws, to achieve compliance in order to respond to a request for personal data; (c) States Parties are encouraged to establish bilateral or multilateral arrangements to facilitate the transfer of personal data.
2. For personal data transferred in accordance with this Convention, States Parties shall ensure that the personal data received are subject to effective and appropriate safeguards in the respective legal frameworks of the States Parties.
3. Subject to paragraph 2 of this article, States Parties may transfer personal data obtained in accordance with this Convention to a third country or an international organization only with the prior

authorization of the original transferring State Party, which may require that the authorization be provided in written form.

Description

Article 36 addresses the protection of personal data during international transfers, ensuring that such data is handled in accordance with applicable national and international laws. Cooperation and the establishment of bilateral or multilateral agreements are essential to facilitate these transfers securely.

Recommendations

1. **Implementation of Clear Legislative Measures:** State Parties should adopt clear legislative measures regulating the transfer of personal data in accordance with national and international laws. This includes ensuring that transfers are only conducted if applicable data protection standards are met (Gulczyńska, 2021).
2. **Establishment of International Agreements:** State Parties are encouraged to establish bilateral or multilateral agreements that facilitate the secure transfer of personal data. These agreements should include provisions to ensure that personal data is adequately protected on both sides of the transfer (Mantovani, 2020).
3. **Effective and Appropriate Safeguards:** State Parties should ensure that personal data received from other State Parties is subject to effective and appropriate safeguards within their respective legal frameworks. This is crucial to maintain trust in international cooperation on personal data protection (Buković, 2020).

Article 37. Extradition

Original Text

1. This article shall apply to the criminal offences established in accordance with this Convention where the person who is the subject of the request for extradition is present in the territory of the requested State Party, provided that the offence for which extradition is sought is punishable under the domestic law of both the requesting State Party and the requested State Party. When the extradition is sought for the purpose of serving a final sentence of imprisonment or another form of detention imposed in respect of an extraditable offence, the requested State Party may grant the extradition in accordance with domestic law. [agreed ad referendum]

2. Notwithstanding paragraph 1 of this article, a State Party whose law so permits may grant the extradition of a person for any of the criminal offences established in accordance with this Convention that are not punishable under its own domestic law. [agreed ad referendum]
3. If the request for extradition includes several separate criminal offences, at least one of which is extraditable under this article and some of which are not extraditable by reason of their period of imprisonment but are related to offences established in accordance with this Convention, the requested State Party may apply this article also in respect of those offences. [agreed ad referendum]
4. Each of the offences to which this article applies shall be deemed to be included as an extraditable offence in any extradition treaty existing between States Parties. States Parties undertake to include such offences as extraditable offences in every extradition treaty to be concluded between them.
4. If a State Party that makes extradition conditional on the existence of a treaty receives a request for extradition from another State Party with which it has no extradition treaty, it may consider this Convention the legal basis for extradition in respect of any offence to which this article applies. [agreed ad referendum]
5. States Parties that make extradition conditional on the existence of a treaty shall: [agreed ad referendum] (a) At the time of deposit of their instruments of ratification, acceptance or approval of or accession to this Convention, inform the Secretary-General of the United Nations whether they will take this Convention as the legal basis for cooperation in extradition with other States Parties to this Convention; and [agreed ad referendum] (b) If they do not take this Convention as the legal basis for cooperation in extradition, seek, where appropriate, to conclude treaties on extradition with other States Parties to this Convention in order to implement this article. [agreed ad referendum]
6. States Parties that do not make extradition conditional on the existence of a treaty shall recognize offences to which this article applies as extraditable offences between themselves. [agreed ad referendum]
7. Extradition shall be subject to the conditions provided for by the domestic law of the requested State Party or by applicable extradition treaties, including, inter alia, conditions in relation to the minimum penalty requirement for extradition and the grounds upon which the requested State Party may refuse extradition. [agreed ad referendum]

8. States Parties shall, subject to their domestic law, endeavour to expedite extradition procedures and to simplify evidentiary requirements relating thereto in respect of any offence to which this article applies. [agreed ad referendum]
9. Subject to the provisions of its domestic law and its extradition treaties, the requested State Party may, upon being satisfied that the circumstances so warrant and are urgent, and at the request of the requesting State Party, including when the request is transmitted through existing channels of the International Criminal Police Organization, take a person whose extradition is sought and who is present in its territory into custody or take other appropriate measures to ensure the person's presence at extradition proceedings. [agreed ad referendum]
10. A State Party in whose territory an alleged offender is found, if it does not extradite such person in respect of an offence to which this article applies solely on the ground that the person is one of its nationals, shall, at the request of the State Party seeking extradition, be obliged to submit the case without undue delay to its competent authorities for the purpose of prosecution. Those authorities shall take their decisions and conduct their proceedings in the same manner as in the case of any other offence of a comparable nature under the domestic law of that State Party. The States Parties concerned shall cooperate with each other, in particular on procedural and evidentiary aspects, to ensure the efficiency of such prosecution. [agreed ad referendum]
11. Whenever a State Party is permitted under its domestic law to extradite or otherwise surrender one of its nationals only upon the condition that the person will be returned to that State Party to serve the sentence imposed as a result of the trial or proceedings for which the extradition or surrender of the person was sought and that State Party and the State Party seeking the extradition of the person agree with this option and other terms that they may deem appropriate, such conditional extradition or surrender shall be sufficient to discharge the obligation set forth in paragraph 11 of this article. [agreed ad referendum]
12. If extradition, sought for purposes of enforcing a sentence, is refused because the person sought is a national of the requested State Party, the requested State Party shall, if its domestic law so permits and in conformity with the requirements of such law, upon application of the requesting State Party, consider the enforcement of the sentence imposed under the domestic law of the requesting State Party or the remainder thereof. [agreed ad referendum]

13. Any person regarding whom proceedings are being carried out in connection with any of the offences to which this article applies shall be guaranteed fair treatment at all stages of the proceedings, including enjoyment of all the rights and guarantees provided by the domestic law of the State Party in the territory of which that person is present. [agreed ad referendum]
14. Nothing in this Convention shall be interpreted as imposing an obligation to extradite if the requested State Party has substantial grounds for believing that the request has been made for the purpose of prosecuting or punishing a person on account of that person's sex, race, language, religion, nationality, ethnic origin or political opinions, or that compliance with the request would cause prejudice to that person's position for any one of these reasons.
15. States Parties may not refuse a request for extradition on the sole ground that the offence is also considered to involve fiscal matters. [agreed ad referendum]
16. Before refusing extradition, the requested State Party shall, where appropriate, consult with the requesting State Party to provide it with ample opportunity to present its opinions and to provide information relevant to its allegation. [agreed ad referendum]
17. The requested State Party shall inform the requesting State Party of its decision with regard to the extradition. The requested State Party shall inform the requesting State Party of any reason for refusal of extradition unless the requested State Party is prevented from doing so by its domestic law or its international legal obligations.
18. Each State Party shall, at the time of signature or when depositing its instrument of ratification, acceptance, approval or accession, communicate to the Secretary-General of the United Nations the name and address of an authority responsible for making or receiving requests for extradition or provisional arrest. The Secretary-General shall set up and keep updated a register of authorities so designated by the States Parties. Each State Party shall ensure that the details held in the register are correct at all times.
19. States Parties shall seek to conclude bilateral and multilateral agreements or arrangements to carry out or to enhance the effectiveness of extradition. [agreed ad referendum]

Description

Article 37 addresses extradition as a vital mechanism for international cooperation in combating cybercrime. It establishes the procedures and conditions under which

State Parties can request and grant the extradition of individuals accused of cybercrimes.

Recommendations

1. **Adoption of Clear Legislative Measures:** State Parties should adopt clear legislative measures defining the procedures and conditions for extradition, ensuring compliance with applicable international and national standards (Asllani, 2013).
2. **Simplification of Procedures:** It is crucial to simplify extradition procedures and evidentiary requirements to expedite international cooperation. This includes eliminating bureaucratic barriers and implementing technologies that facilitate the exchange of information (Kennedy & Warren, 2020).
3. **Safeguards for Human Rights:** State Parties must ensure that extradition procedures respect the human rights of requested individuals, providing fair treatment and protection against potential abuses or unjustified persecutions (Wijayath, 2018).

Article 39. Transfer of criminal proceedings

Original Text

1. States Parties shall consider the possibility of transferring to one another proceedings for the criminal prosecution of an offence established in accordance with this Convention where such a transfer is deemed to be in the interests of the proper administration of justice, particularly in cases where several jurisdictions are involved, with a view to concentrating the prosecution.
2. If a State Party that makes the transfer of criminal proceedings conditional on the existence of a treaty receives a request for transfer from another State Party with which it has no treaty in this matter, it may consider this Convention as the legal basis for the transfer of criminal proceedings in respect of any offence to which this article applies. [agreed ad referendum]

Description

Article 39 addresses the transfer of criminal proceedings between State Parties, an essential measure for the efficient administration of justice in cybercrime cases involving multiple jurisdictions. This practice can prevent jurisdictional conflicts and ensure that cases are prosecuted effectively and consistently.

Recommendations

1. **Implementation of Clear Legislative Measures:** State Parties should adopt clear legislative measures that facilitate the transfer of criminal proceedings, ensuring that national and international regulations are properly applied. This is crucial for handling cybercrime cases that cross borders and affect multiple jurisdictions (Voynova, 2015).
2. **Establishment of International Agreements:** It is recommended that State Parties establish bilateral or multilateral agreements to facilitate the transfer of criminal proceedings. These agreements should include detailed protocols for cooperation and information exchange between judicial authorities (Klevtsov, 2020).
3. **Safeguards for Human Rights:** It is fundamental that the transfer of criminal proceedings respects the human rights of the accused. State Parties should ensure that procedures are conducted fairly and equitably, protecting the procedural rights of the individuals involved (Hursevich, 2019).

Article 40. General principles and procedures relating to mutual legal assistance

Original Text

1. States Parties shall afford one another the widest measure of mutual legal assistance in investigations, prosecutions and judicial proceedings in relation to the offences established in accordance with this Convention, and for the purposes of the collection of evidence in electronic form of offences established in accordance with this Convention, as well as of serious crimes. [agreed in informals]
2. Mutual legal assistance shall be afforded to the fullest extent possible under relevant laws, treaties, agreements and arrangements of the requested State Party with respect to investigations, prosecutions and judicial proceedings in relation to the offences for which a legal person may be held liable in accordance with article 18 of this Convention in the requesting State Party.
3. Mutual legal assistance to be afforded in accordance with this article may be requested for any of the following purposes: (a) Taking evidence or statements from persons; (b) Effecting service of judicial documents; (c) Executing searches and seizures, and freezing; (d) Searching or similarly accessing, seizing or similarly securing, and disclosing electronic data stored by means of an information and communications technology system pursuant to article 44 of this Convention; (e) Collecting traffic data in real time pursuant to article 45

of this Convention; (f) Intercepting content data pursuant to article 46 of this Convention; (g) Examining objects and sites; (h) Providing information, evidentiary items, evidence and expert evaluations; (i) Providing originals or certified copies of relevant documents and records, including government, bank, financial, corporate or business records; (j) Identifying or tracing proceeds of crime, property, instrumentalities or other things for evidentiary purposes; (k) Facilitating the voluntary appearance of persons in the requesting State Party; (l) Recovering proceeds of crime; (m) Any other type of assistance that is not contrary to the domestic law of the requested State Party.

4. Without prejudice to domestic law, the competent authorities of a State Party may, without prior request, transmit information relating to criminal matters to a competent authority in another State Party where they believe that such information could assist the authority in undertaking or successfully concluding inquiries and criminal proceedings or could result in a request formulated by the latter State Party pursuant to this Convention.
5. The transmission of information pursuant to paragraph 4 of this article shall be without prejudice to inquiries and criminal proceedings in the State of the competent authorities providing the information. The competent authorities receiving the information shall comply with a request that said information remain confidential, even temporarily, or with restrictions on its use. However, this shall not prevent the receiving State Party from disclosing in its proceedings information that is exculpatory to an accused person. In such a case, the receiving State Party shall notify the transmitting State Party prior to the disclosure and, if so requested, consult with the transmitting State Party. If, in an exceptional case, advance notice is not possible, the receiving State Party shall inform the transmitting State Party of the disclosure without delay.
6. The provisions of this article shall not affect obligations under any other treaty, bilateral or multilateral, that governs or will govern, in whole or in part, mutual legal assistance.
7. Paragraphs 8 to 31 of this article shall apply to requests made pursuant to this article if the States Parties in question are not bound by a treaty on mutual legal assistance. If those States Parties are bound by such a treaty, the corresponding provisions of that treaty shall apply unless the States Parties agree to apply paragraphs 8 to 31 of this article in lieu thereof. States Parties are strongly encouraged to apply the provisions of those paragraphs if they facilitate cooperation.

8. States Parties may decline to render assistance pursuant to this article on the ground of absence of dual criminality. However, the requested State Party may, when it deems appropriate, provide assistance, to the extent it decides at its discretion, irrespective of whether the conduct would constitute an offence under the domestic law of the requested State Party. Assistance may be refused when requests involve matters of a de minimis nature or matters for which the cooperation or assistance sought is available under other provisions of this Convention.
9. A person who is being detained or is serving a sentence in the territory of one State Party and whose presence in another State Party is requested for purposes of identification, testimony or otherwise providing assistance in obtaining evidence for investigations, prosecutions or judicial proceedings in relation to offences established in accordance with this Convention may be transferred if the following conditions are met: (a) The person freely gives informed consent; (b) The competent authorities of both States Parties agree, subject to such conditions as those States Parties may deem appropriate.
10. For the purposes of paragraph 9 of this article: (a) The State Party to which the person is transferred shall have the authority and obligation to keep the person transferred in custody, unless otherwise requested or authorized by the State Party from which the person was transferred; (b) The State Party to which the person is transferred shall, without delay, implement its obligation to return the person to the custody of the State Party from which the person was transferred as agreed beforehand, or as otherwise agreed, by the competent authorities of both States Parties; (c) The State Party to which the person is transferred shall not require the State Party from which the person was transferred to initiate extradition proceedings for the return of the person; (d) The person transferred shall receive credit for service of the sentence being served in the State from which the person was transferred for time spent in the custody of the State Party to which the person was transferred.
11. Unless the State Party from which a person is to be transferred in accordance with paragraphs 9 and 10 of this article so agrees, that person, regardless of the person's nationality, shall not be prosecuted, detained, punished or subjected to any other restriction of liberty in the territory of the State to which that person is transferred in respect of acts, omissions or convictions prior to the person's departure from the territory of the State from which the person was transferred.
12. (a) Each State Party shall designate a central authority or authorities that shall have the responsibility and power to receive requests for

mutual legal assistance and either to execute them or to transmit them to the competent authorities for execution. Where a State Party has a special region or territory with a separate system of mutual legal assistance, it may designate a distinct central authority that shall have the same function for that region or territory; (b) Central authorities shall ensure the speedy and proper execution or transmission of the requests received. Where the central authority transmits the request to a competent authority for execution, it shall encourage the speedy and proper execution of the request by the competent authority; (c) The Secretary-General of the United Nations shall be notified of the central authority designated for this purpose at the time each State Party deposits its instrument of ratification, acceptance or approval of or accession to this Convention, and shall set up and keep updated a register of central authorities designated by the States Parties. Each State Party shall ensure that the details held in the register are correct at all times; (d) Requests for mutual legal assistance and any communication related thereto shall be transmitted to the central authorities designated by the States Parties. This requirement shall be without prejudice to the right of a State Party to require that such requests and communications be addressed to it through diplomatic channels and, in urgent circumstances, where the States Parties agree, through the International Criminal Police Organization, if possible.

13. Requests shall be made in writing or, where possible, by any means capable of producing a written record, in a language acceptable to the requested State Party, under conditions allowing that State Party to establish authenticity. The Secretary-General of the United Nations shall be notified of the language or languages acceptable to each State Party at the time it deposits its instrument of ratification, acceptance or approval of or accession to this Convention. In urgent circumstances and where agreed by the States Parties, requests may be made orally, but shall be confirmed in writing forthwith.
14. Where not prohibited by their respective laws, central authorities of States Parties are encouraged to transmit and receive requests for mutual legal assistance, and communications related thereto, as well as evidence, in electronic form under conditions allowing the requested State Party to establish authenticity and ensuring the security of communications.
15. A request for mutual legal assistance shall contain: (a) The identity of the authority making the request; (b) The subject matter and nature of the investigation, prosecution or judicial proceeding to which the request relates and the name and functions of the authority conducting

the investigation, prosecution or judicial proceeding; (c) A summary of the relevant facts, except in relation to requests for the purpose of service of judicial documents; (d) A description of the assistance sought and details of any particular procedure that the requesting State Party wishes to be followed; (e) Where possible and appropriate, the identity, location and nationality of any person concerned, as well as the country of origin, description and location of any item or accounts concerned; [agreed in informals] (f) Where applicable, the time period for which the evidence, information or other assistance is sought; and [agreed in informals] (g) The purpose for which the evidence, information or other assistance is sought. [agreed in informals]

16. The requested State Party may request additional information when it appears necessary for the execution of the request in accordance with its domestic law or when it can facilitate such execution.
17. A request shall be executed in accordance with the domestic law of the requested State Party and, to the extent not contrary to the domestic law of the requested State Party and where possible, in accordance with the procedures specified in the request.
18. Wherever possible and consistent with fundamental principles of domestic law, when an individual is in the territory of a State Party and has to be heard as a witness, victim or expert by the judicial authorities of another State Party, the first State Party may, at the request of the other, permit the hearing to take place by videoconference if it is not possible or desirable for the individual in question to appear in person in the territory of the requesting State Party. States Parties may agree that the hearing shall be conducted by a judicial authority of the requesting State Party and attended by a judicial authority of the requested State Party. If the requested State Party does not have access to the technical means necessary for holding a videoconference, such means may be provided by the requesting State Party, upon mutual agreement.
19. The requesting State Party shall not transmit or use information or evidence furnished by the requested State Party for investigations, prosecutions or judicial proceedings other than those stated in the request without the prior consent of the requested State Party. Nothing in this paragraph shall prevent the requesting State Party from disclosing in its proceedings information or evidence that is exculpatory to an accused person. In the latter case, the requesting State Party shall notify the requested State Party prior to the disclosure and, if so requested, consult with the requested State Party. If, in an exceptional case, advance notice is not possible, the requesting State

Party shall inform the requested State Party of the disclosure without delay.

20. The requesting State Party may require that the requested State Party keep confidential the fact and substance of the request, except to the extent necessary to execute the request. If the requested State Party cannot comply with the requirement of confidentiality, it shall promptly inform the requesting State Party.
21. Mutual legal assistance may be refused: (a) If the request is not made in conformity with the provisions of this article; (b) If the requested State Party considers that execution of the request is likely to prejudice its sovereignty, security, ordre public or other essential interests; (c) If the authorities of the requested State Party would be prohibited by its domestic law from carrying out the action requested with regard to any similar offence, had it been subject to investigation, prosecution or judicial proceedings under their own jurisdiction; (d) If it would be contrary to the legal system of the requested State Party relating to mutual legal assistance for the request to be granted.
22. Nothing in this Convention shall be interpreted as imposing an obligation to afford mutual legal assistance if the requested State Party has substantial grounds for believing that the request has been made for the purpose of prosecuting or punishing a person on account of that person's sex, race, language, religion, nationality, ethnic origin or political opinions, or that compliance with the request would cause prejudice to that person's position for any one of these reasons.
23. States Parties may not refuse a request for mutual legal assistance on the sole ground that the offence is also considered to involve fiscal matters.
24. States Parties shall not decline to render mutual legal assistance pursuant to this article on the ground of bank secrecy.
25. Reasons shall be given for any refusal of mutual legal assistance.
26. The requested State Party shall execute the request for mutual legal assistance as soon as possible and shall take as full account as possible of any deadlines suggested by the requesting State Party and for which reasons are given, preferably in the request. The requested State Party shall respond to reasonable requests by the requesting State Party on the status, and progress in its handling, of the request. The requesting State Party shall promptly inform the requested State Party when the assistance sought is no longer required.
27. Mutual legal assistance may be postponed by the requested State Party on the ground that it interferes with an ongoing investigation, prosecution or judicial proceeding.

28. Before refusing a request pursuant to paragraph 21 of this article or postponing its execution pursuant to paragraph 27 of this article, the requested State Party shall consult with the requesting State Party to consider whether assistance may be granted subject to such terms and conditions as it deems necessary. If the requesting State Party accepts assistance subject to those conditions, it shall comply with the conditions.
29. Without prejudice to the application of paragraph 11 of this article, a witness, expert or other person who, at the request of the requesting State Party, consents to give evidence in a proceeding or to assist in an investigation, prosecution or judicial proceeding in the territory of the requesting State Party shall not be prosecuted, detained, punished or subjected to any other restriction of the person's liberty in that territory in respect of acts, omissions or convictions prior to the person's departure from the territory of the requested State Party. Such safe conduct shall cease when the witness, expert or other person having had, for a period of 15 consecutive days or for any period agreed upon by the States Parties from the date on which the person has been officially informed that the presence of the person is no longer required by the judicial authorities, an opportunity of leaving, has nevertheless remained voluntarily in the territory of the requesting State Party or, having left it, has returned of the person's own free will.
30. The ordinary costs of executing a request shall be borne by the requested State Party, unless otherwise agreed by the States Parties concerned. If expenses of a substantial or extraordinary nature are or will be required to fulfil the request, the States Parties shall consult to determine the terms and conditions under which the request will be executed, as well as the manner in which the costs shall be borne.
31. The requested State Party: (a) Shall provide to the requesting State Party copies of government records, documents or information in its possession that under its domestic law are available to the general public; (b) May, at its discretion, provide to the requesting State Party, in whole, in part or subject to such conditions as it deems appropriate, copies of any government records, documents or information in its possession that under its domestic law are not available to the general public.
32. States Parties shall consider, as may be necessary, the possibility of concluding bilateral or multilateral agreements or arrangements that would serve the purposes of, give practical effect to or enhance the provisions of this article.

Description

Article 40 establishes the principles and procedures for mutual legal assistance in investigations and prosecutions related to cybercrimes. International cooperation in this area is essential to effectively combat cybercrime, given the transnational nature of many of these offenses.

Recommendations

1. **Implementation of Efficient Measures:** State Parties should adopt clear legislative measures and procedures that facilitate mutual legal assistance in cybercrime investigations. This includes establishing efficient protocols for the collection and exchange of electronic evidence (Hunton, 2012).
2. **Promotion of International Collaboration:** It is recommended to promote international collaboration through the conclusion of bilateral and multilateral agreements that facilitate cooperation in mutual legal assistance. These agreements should include specific provisions for data protection and the confidentiality of shared information (Wilson, 2008).
3. **Safeguards for Human Rights:** State Parties must ensure that mutual legal assistance procedures respect the human rights of all parties involved. This includes guaranteeing fair and equitable treatment during proceedings and protecting the procedural rights of the accused (Mabeka & Cassim, 2023).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The Knowmad Institute urges the Ad Hoc Committee to consider these recommendations to ensure that the proposed convention not only effectively combats cybercrime but also respects and protects human rights and fundamental freedoms. Implementing these recommendations will promote balanced and effective international cooperation while guaranteeing human dignity and sustainable development.

Additionally, the convention must consider and mitigate any potential misuse of surveillance technologies. We are concerned that the convention's approach could be interpreted and used to justify mass surveillance that infringes on fundamental rights to privacy and free movement, especially in the Global North, and that this would disproportionately affect migrant and displaced populations. Clear and strict safeguards must be established to prevent the instrumentalization of these measures against vulnerable groups, ensuring that any actions taken under this convention are carried out with full respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms in accordance with the principles established in the United Nations Charter.

Cybercrime is a phenomenon that can affect daily activities, compromise privacy, and violate the rights of those who use technologies and the internet. Given its range (from economic fraud to cyberbullying and the most severe offenses related to child sexual exploitation and others that deeply endanger and violate people's rights and dignity), it is essential that the Comprehensive International Convention on Countering the Use of Information and Communication Technologies for Criminal Purposes explicitly references international human rights frameworks, such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) of the United Nations. This will ensure that measures against cybercrime align with international human rights standards, reinforce their legitimacy, and foster cooperation among Member States.

Secondly, continuous updating of definitions and measures against cybercrime is necessary, as the dynamics of coexistence, socialization, transaction, and even decision-making and development of activities in the social, political, and cultural spheres in cyberspace are renewed and transformed rapidly. This has created gaps and inequalities in terms of access to and delivery of justice when fundamental rights are violated. This also implies clarifying key terms, starting with cybercrime and its modalities, to avoid ambiguous use that could lead to misleading interpretations. It is proposed that examples be used when technical terms are employed.

It is essential to clarify the scope of the definition of offenses, specifying that these can be committed by natural persons, legal entities, and state and parastatal entities. It includes espionage perpetrated by these entities against activists, journalists, and other civil society actors.

It is crucial to implement educational and awareness programs on ICT security and cybercrime prevention. These programs should be designed to inform users about the risks associated with ICT use and include recommendations and preventive measures in the various spheres of users' development. It is also essential to have procedures to recover and preserve information, as necessary, to minimize the impact of any incident in cyberspace or hybrid space.

In this regard, another critical aspect is comprehensive support for victims of cybercrimes, including counseling and legal assistance services. For this to be effective, prevention programs should be backed by continuous human rights training for law enforcement officers, judges, prosecutors, and victim support staff, such as doctors, psychologists, and social workers, on the rights and needs of victims to foster a culture of empathy and support, aiming to promote a culture of respect and protection in all related actions and decisions.

The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights enshrined the right to access justice. Therefore, Member States must ensure that individuals (regardless of nationality, ethnic origin, migratory background, gender, creed, or ideology) can access and defend their rights in fair and impartial processes. This relates to the sanctions resulting from these processes, which must be proportional and effective, as not all cybercrimes have the same impact. Therefore, sanctions can range from complementary measures linked to cybersecurity education programs, deterrent economic penalties for restitution to cybercrime victims, and even imprisonment.

We call on Member States to maintain a human rights-centered approach when formulating and applying measures against cybercrime, protecting and promoting the dignity of every individual. Only then can we build a safe and just digital environment for all.

European Institute for Multidisciplinary Studies on Human Rights and Sciences - Knowmad Institut.

Grupo Especial de Trabajo:

Ob. Martin Ignacio Díaz Velásquez, Prof. Jorge Vicente Paladines, Dra. Leticia Fuentes Vera, Ing. Jesús Alfredo Ribero Faria, MSc. Oscar Hugo Espin García, Rev. Daniela Kreher, MSc. Ludwing Moncada Bellorin.

REFERENCES

1. Ahsan, M., Nygard, K. E., Gomes, R., Chowdhury, M. M., & Rifat, N. (2022). Cybersecurity threats and their mitigation approaches using machine learning—A review. *Journal of Cybersecurity and Privacy*, 2(3), 527-555. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcp2030027>
2. Ali, A., Khan, I., & Bashir, S. (2022). Need of international legislation regarding cyber crimes: Pakistan perspective. *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*, 4(2), 45-55. <https://doi.org/10.52567/pjsr.v4i2.608>
3. Aldridge, J., Stevens, A., & Barratt, M. J. (2017). Will growth in cryptomarket drug buying increase the harms of illicit drugs? *Addiction*, 113(5), 789-796. <https://doi.org/10.1111/add.13899>
4. Ajoy, P. B. (2022). Effectiveness of criminal law in tackling cybercrime: A critical analysis. *Scholars International Journal of Law, Crime and Justice*, 5(2), 75-85. <https://doi.org/10.36348/sijlcrj.2022.v05i02.005>

5. Aulia, A. (2023). Adoption of the law on information and electronic transactions against cyber crime. *Scholars International Journal of Law, Crime and Justice*, 6(3), 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.36348/sijlcyj.2023.v06i03.001>
6. Balajanov, E. (2018). Setting the minimum age of criminal responsibility for cybercrime. *International Review of Law, Computers & Technology*, 32(1), 102-115. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600869.2018.1417764>
7. Brenner, S. W., & Clarke, L. L. (2009). Combatting cybercrime through distributed security. *International Journal of Intercultural Information Management*, 1(3), 259. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/76622895.pdf>
8. Broadhurst, R. (2017). Cybercrime: Thieves, swindlers, bandits and privateers in cyberspace. SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3009574>
9. Bunga, D. (2019). Legal response to cybercrime in global and national dimensions. *Padjadjaran Journal of International Law*, 6(1), 45-57. <https://doi.org/10.22304/pjih.v6n1.a4>
10. Bunga, D., & Hiariej, O. S. (2019). Cyberbullying on children in victimology perspective. *Scholars International Journal of Law, Crime and Justice*, 2(2), 116-121. <https://doaj.org/article/74dfa3150c9d4afdabdb5a24672dae82>
11. Caneppele, S., & Aebi, M. F. (2017). Crime drop or police recording flop? On the relationship between the decrease of offline crime and the increase of online and hybrid crimes. *Policing: A Journal of Policy and Practice*, 13(1), 66-79. <https://doi.org/10.1093/police/pax055>
12. Cerezo, A., Lopez, J., & Patel, A. (2007). International cooperation to fight transnational cybercrime. *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Advanced Communication Technology (ICACT)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/WDFIA.2007.7>
13. Citron, D. K., & Franks, M. A. (2014). Criminalizing revenge porn. *Wake Forest Law Review*, 49, 345+. U of Maryland Legal Studies Research Paper No. 2014-1. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2368946>
14. Clough, J. (2015). Principles of cybercrime: Interception of data. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139540803.007>
15. Cross, D. (2017). A human rights-based approach to community justice: Adding value to desistance focused practice. *European Journal of Probation*, 9(2), 67-84. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2066220317719801>
16. Curtis, J., & Oxburgh, G. (2023). Understanding cybercrime in 'real world' policing and law enforcement. *The Police Journal*, 96(4), 573-592. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0032258X221107584>

17. Da-Yu Kao, E., Chang, E.-C., & Tsai, F. (2019). Extracting suspicious IP addresses from WhatsApp network traffic in cybercrime investigations. *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Advanced Communication Technology (ICACT)*. <https://doi.org/10.23919/ICACT.2019.8701941>
18. Dragomir, B. (2022). Mechanisms of international cooperation against cybercrime. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Cybercrime*, 70(1), 55-68. <https://doi.org/10.36997/ppdd2022.70>
19. ECPAT International. (2016). Orientaciones terminológicas para la protección de niñas, niños y adolescentes contra la explotación y el abuso sexuales. ECPAT Luxembourg. https://ecpat.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Terminology-guidelines_Spanish_version-electronica_FINAL.pdf
20. Feldle, J. (2020). Zivilrechtliche Haftung im automatisierten Straßenverkehr – Hackerangriffe, Sicherheitserwartungen und erlaubte Nebentätigkeiten. *Nomos*. <https://doi.org/10.5771/9783748920984-199>
21. Geldenhuys, K. (2021). Spyware. *Servamus Community-Based Safety and Security Magazine*, 114(10), 15-17. https://doi.org/10.10520/ejc-servamus_v114_n10_a5
22. Grauer, K. (2022). The 2022 crypto crime report. *Chainalysis*. <https://go.chainalysis.com/rs/503-FAP-074/images/Crypto-Crime-Report-2022.pdf>
23. Gunarto, G., Jainah, J., & Mashdurohatun, A. (2023). Legal reconstruction of trafficking victim protection based on justice value. *Scholars International Journal of Law, Crime and Justice*, 6(5), 25-32. <https://doi.org/10.36348/sijlclj.2023.v06i05.005>
24. Han, Y. (2023). Research and application of pseudo-information detection technology based on computer information hiding. *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Advanced Communication Technology (ICACT)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCTCS58815.2023.00067>
25. Henry, N., Flynn, A., & Powell, A. (2020). Technology-facilitated domestic and sexual violence: A review. *Violence Against Women*, 26(7), 761-788. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077801219841445>
26. Holt, T. (2018). Regulating cybercrime through law enforcement and industry mechanisms. *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 678(1), 140-157. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716218783679>
27. Hursevich, A. (2019). Ube international legal cooperation of the prosecutor general's office of the republic of belarus in the fight against cybercrime

- and typical examples of committing such crimes. *RAESMPCE*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.54275/raesmpce.v11i2.96>
28. Irawan, J., Nathaniel, A., & Jonathan, S. (2022). Juridical analysis about cyberbullying cases by child perpetrators against child victims. *De Jure: Jurnal Hukum Dan Siyasah*, 22(1), 17-32. <https://doi.org/10.30641/dejure.2022.v22.17-32>
29. Interpol. (2022). Terminología apropiada. Recuperado de <https://www.interpol.int/es/Delitos/Delitos-contramenores/Terminologia-apropiada>
30. Kagita, M. K., Thilakarathne, N., Gadekallu, T. R., Maddikunta, P. K. R., & Singh, S. (2020). A review on cyber crimes on the internet of things. *ArXiv*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2009.05708>
31. Kaur, S. (2021). Security in cyber crime. *International Journal of Recent Advances in Science and Technology*, 9(5), 123-135. <https://doi.org/10.22214/ijraset.2021.38023>
32. Kennedy, S., & Warren, I. (2020). The legal geographies of extradition and sovereign power. *Internet Policy Review*, 9(3), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.14763/2020.3.1496>
33. Khan, S., Saleh, T., Dorasamy, M., Tan Swee Leng, O., & Gale Vergara, R. (2022). A systematic literature review on cybercrime legislation. *F1000Research*, 11, 971. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.123098.1>
34. Klevtsov, K. (2020). International cooperation in the fight against cybercrime: Current state and development prospects. *SSRN*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3728311>
35. Knowmad Institut. (2023). TERCERA SESIÓN: COOPERACIÓN INTERNACIONAL, ASISTENCIA TÉCNICA, MEDIDAS DE PREVENCIÓN Y MECANISMO DE APLICACIÓN. Recuperado de https://www.unodc.org/documents/Cybercrime/AdHocCommittee/Second_session/Documents/Knowmad-ES_3rd_Session.pdf
36. Krastev, D. B. (2022). Mechanisms of international cooperation against cybercrime. *International Journal of Cybersecurity*, 70(2), 155-167. <https://doi.org/10.36997/ppdd2022.70>
37. Lobach, D. V., Shestopal, S. S., & Smirnova, N. L. (2021). The phenomenon of cyber crime in the focus of conceptual legal analysis. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 6(3), 385-392. <https://doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2021.06.03.77>
38. Mabeka, N. Q., & Cassim, F. (2023). Interpreting the provisions of the Cybercrimes Act 19 of 2020 in the context of civil procedure: A future journey. *Obiter*, 44(1). <https://doi.org/10.17159/obiter.v44i1.15886>

39. Mantovani, M. (2020). Contractual obligations as a tool for international transfers of personal data under the GDPR. *SSRN*.
<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3522426>
40. McGlynn, C., & Rackley, E. (2017). Image-based sexual abuse. *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies*, 37(3), 534-561.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/ojls/gqw033>
41. Meier, B. M., Huffstetler, H. E., & de Mesquita, J. B. (2020). Monitoring and review to assess human rights implementation. *International Journal of Human Rights*, 24(3), 256-270.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780197528297.003.0008>
42. Montal, F., & Pauselli, G. (2023). Is the bad news about compliance bad news about human rights? Evidence from the Inter-American Commission on Human Rights. *International Studies Quarterly*, 67(1), 85-97.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/isq/sqad027>
43. Naciones Unidas. (1966). Pacto Internacional de Derechos Civiles y Políticos. Recuperado de <https://www.ohchr.org/es/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/international-covenant-civil-and-political-rights>
44. Naciones Unidas. (1966). Pacto Internacional de Derechos Civiles y Políticos. Recuperado de https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/ccpr_sp.pdf
45. Naciones Unidas. (2016). Promoción, protección y disfrute de los derechos humanos en Internet. A/HRC/32/L.20. Recuperado de https://ap.ohchr.org/documents/S/HRC/d_res_dec/A_HRC_32_L20.pdf
46. Nurahman, D. (2019). Kebijakan penegakan hukum cybercrime dan pembuktian yuridis dalam sistem hukum pidana nasional. *Jurnal Keadilan*, 17(2), 270-284. <https://doi.org/10.37090/keadilan.v17i2.270>
47. Nurahman, D. (2020). Cybercrime Policies: Juridical Evidence and Law Enforcement Policies. *CCER*, 101.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.4108/eai.26-9-2020.2302579>
48. PTACC | Police Treatment and Community Collaborative. (2022). Best practices in law enforcement and community responses. Recuperado de <https://ptaccollaborative.org/>
49. Ruslan, A. R. (2023). International legal regulation of the fight against cybercrime. *Journal of International Law*, 24(3), 24-30.
<https://doi.org/10.37399/issn2072-909x.2023.4.24-30>
50. Sabu, J., Ananthanarayanan, S., Gopan, A., G. S., & Murali, S. (2023). Advanced keylogger with keystroke dynamics. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Information and Communication Technology*.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICICT57646.2023.10134044>

51. Sarkar, G., & Shukla, S. (2023). Behavioral analysis of cybercrime: Paving the way for effective policing strategies. *Journal of Economic Criminology*, 2, 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconc.2023.100034>
52. Saxena, M. (2023). Impact of cybercrime on e-governance. Is cybercrime affecting the confidentiality of government data? *International Journal of Cyber Criminology*. <https://doi.org/10.21275/sr231111140516>
53. Setiawahyudi, A. (2015). Kendala pertanggungjawaban pidana terhadap pelaku pencurian uang di bank melalui internet berdasarkan Undang-undang Nomor 11 Tahun 2008 Tentang Informasi dan Transaksi Elektronik. *Majalah Hukum*, 21(2), 145-167. <https://dx.doi.org/10.30996/mk.v0i0.2116>
54. Skulysh, I. (2014). International legal cooperation in the field of combating cybercrime. *Journal of Law and Political Sciences*, 10(1), 272-432. [https://doi.org/10.37750/2616-6798.2014.1\(10\).272432](https://doi.org/10.37750/2616-6798.2014.1(10).272432)
55. Snail, S. (2009). Cyber crime in South Africa - Hacking, cracking, and other unlawful online activities. *Journal of Information Law & Technology*, 10(2), 127-145. <https://dblp.org/rec/journals/jilt/Snail09.html>
56. Sprott, J. B. (2006). The use of custody for failing to comply with a disposition cases under the Young Offenders Act. *Canadian Journal of Criminology and Criminal Justice*, 48(3), 251-271. <https://doi.org/10.1353/ccj.2006.0043>
57. Szongoth, R., & Vetter, D. (2018). Nemzetközi bűnügyi együttműködés a kiberbűnözés területén. *Budapesti Szemle*, 7-8(1), 45-60. <https://doi.org/10.38146/bsz.2018.7-8.1>
58. Teichmann, F., & Wittmann, C. (2022). When is a law firm liable for a data breach? An exploration into the legal liability of ransomware and cybersecurity. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 29(3), 819-832. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jfc-04-2022-0093>
59. Tiutiuhin, V. I. (2022). Conviction as one of the means of criminal responsibility. *Journal of Law and Political Sciences*, 18(1), 267-249. <https://doi.org/10.21564/2311-9640.2022.18.267249>
60. UNODC. (2021). World drug report 2021. *United Nations: Office on Drugs and Crime*. <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/data-and-analysis/wdr2021.html>
61. Varshney, S., Munjal, D., Jash, I., Bhattacharya, O., & Saboo, S. (2020). Cyber crime awareness and corresponding countermeasures. *SSRN*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3601807>

62. Veresha, R. (2018). Preventive measures against computer related crimes. *Interdisciplinary Management Research*, 14, 227-243. <https://doi.org/10.32914/I.51.3-4.7>
63. Voynova, R. (2015). Comparison of the transfer of criminal proceeding with other forms of international legal cooperation in criminal matters. *Sciendo*. <https://doi.org/10.1515/kbo-2015-0091>
64. Weber, R. (2009). Internet of things–Need for a new legal environment? *Computer Law & Security Review*, 25(6), 522-527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2009.09.002>
65. Wicki-Birchler, D. (2020). The Budapest Convention and the General Data Protection Regulation: acting in concert to curb cybercrime?. *Int. Cybersecur. Law Rev.* 1, 63–72. <https://doi.org/10.1365/s43439-020-00012-5>
66. Wilson, N. (2008). Forensics in cyber-space: The legal challenges. *International Journal of Digital Crime and Forensics*, 3(1), 56-70. <https://doi.org/10.4108/E-FORENSICS.2008.2926>
67. Wingfield, T., & Wingo, H. (2021). International law for cyberspace. *Oxford Handbook of Cybersecurity*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198800682.013.37>

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